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Abbreviations

WP	Work Package
LL	Living Lab
JRAs	Joint Research Activities
LLL	Living Lab Lexicon
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
LLBM	Living Lab Business Model
BMC	Business Model Canvas
B2B	Business-to-Business
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
PCP	Pre-commercial Procurement
TA	Transnational Access
CA	Contract Agreement
BA	Bilateral Agreement
OLLD	Open Living Lab Days
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators

Executive summary

Living Labs have emerged as resilient research and innovation infrastructures and have been shown to be a “key” to the integration of research and innovation processes in real-life settings. VITALISE creates the first Living Lab Harmonization framework, addressing various aspects of the Living Labs operations and procedures. It aims to facilitate Living Labs to function according to unified and harmonized processes that are easily accessible and exploitable by academic and industry researchers. The current Standard version, being the first complete Living Lab Harmonization guidelines, will facilitate the access of researchers to the provided infrastructures.

This document presents the work performed for the Harmonization of the way Living Labs work for the sixth and final semester of VITALISE. Within the VITALISE project, various Harmonization activities were carried out with consortium partners and external stakeholders, to develop the Standard v1.0, building on the work done for the earlier versions of the Standard (v0.1, v0.2, v0.3, v0.4, v0.5). The first version of the Standard (v0.1) provided an overview of the state-of-the-art information about Living Labs in the VITALISE consortium and served as the foundational deliverable for the VITALISE Standards. The second version of the Standard (v0.2) introduced the process of developing and disseminating a Wiki page that incorporated v0.1 and updated the parts of the Standard that described the data and technologies used in living labs, using a Delphi study method, and collected the initial set of terms for the living lab lexicon. Additionally, during the second semester, the Harmonization Board was established, and a meeting with the Harmonization Body was held. In the third version of the Standard (v0.3) the device and technology taxonomy were updated through a Delphi study, several meetings were held for updating the services and procedures categorization, as well as several activities and sessions for collecting and achieving a preliminary agreement on living lab lexicon terms. Moreover, two templates were developed for the co-creation sessions conducted within the Joint Research Activities (JRAs) and also, during this third semester, the project held its second plenary meeting in Helsinki and the second Harmonization Body meeting. For the fourth version of the Standard (v0.4) a wide range of actions took place, including meetings and activities to update the Living Lab Lexicon terms and LL services, as well as define the Living Lab Innovation and Research phases. In addition, an analysis of the Open Call data was conducted related to stakeholders, services, and devices and some interviews with partners from the consortium and beyond. Furthermore, the finalization and approval of data and devices taxonomy from the Delphi study occurred, alongside the occurrence of the 3rd Harmonization Body meeting and one Harmonization Board meeting in January and February, respectively. Standard Version 0.5 presented a visual tool for the representation of the Living Lab Research and Innovation process. Progress was achieved in the validation of the general KPI table and the proposal of a preliminary set of questions for the self-assessment tool for living labs. Substantial advancements were made in the realm of methods and tools, including a preliminary categorization of the questionnaires and instruments utilized in the JRA pilots. Additionally, some ethics tools, along with templates for Data Controllers Agreements have been specified and presented in this deliverable.

The current Standard Version 1.0 is the first complete and stable version of the Living Lab Harmonization Guidelines. It includes an updated version of the Living Lab Lexicon with an extended list of terms and their definitions as well as the latest version of Living Lab Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). Information was added about the LL key activities, resources, cost structure, partner networks and channels as part of the Living Lab Business Model presentation. The categorization of validated questionnaires used in Living Lab research, was also updated.

1 Introduction

1.1 Description of WP2

Work Package 2 (WP2), “Common Standards, Procedures and Practices” is a core WP for the VITALISE project as it handles all the work and implementation for the Harmonization procedure that is being followed. Some of the main tasks are the establishment of the harmonization procedures within the consortium and beyond, the management and organization of the Harmonization procedure events (Harmonization Body and Board meetings) and the definition and update of the Standards and Key Performance Indicators by identifying and documenting the existing Living Lab processes, and the similarities and differences among the consortium’s Living Lab partners. The Standard Versions were updated every six months until this final version, when the end of the VITALISE project has been reached.

VITALISE Harmonization Body is a wider community of stakeholders consisting of Living Lab researchers and practitioners, healthcare professionals, policy makers and professionals that are interested in research performed in Living Lab infrastructures. VITALISE Harmonization Board aims to coordinate the Harmonization procedures and practices and consists of representatives from each Living Lab in the consortium, independent representatives from the Health and Wellbeing domain as well as policy makers. Representatives of other Health and Wellbeing Living Labs are also encouraged to join. This board have taken decisions regarding the Standard Versions during the VITALISE project.

1.2 Purpose of the document

This document aims to present all the data collection and analysis that has been done between M31-M36 of the VITALISE project regarding the Harmonization activities. Although the deliverable is entitled “Standard Version 6”, it is the final version of the Standard released by the end of the project on M36, and the authors of this document decided that the specific standard should actually be Version 1.0 as it is the first version that includes all the required parts. This document does not only encompasses the Standard Version 1.0 of the Living Labs services, methods and tools, but it is also a more elaborate version that includes the presentation of data collection, activities and analysis. This document will serve as the starting point for the upcoming activities of the ENoLL Harmonization Working Group.

Document Structure

The deliverable is structured as such:

- **Section 1** (this section) provides information regarding the VITALISE project, aspects related to it, and the purpose of the document.
- **Section 2** discusses the activities that were performed during the sixth semester of living lab harmonization framework towards the creation of Standard v1.0
- **Section 3** presents a summary of the changes and new additions that were made to the final version of the standard.
- **Section 4** includes all the information that will constitute the Standard Version 1.0. This Section is a coherent version of the Standard and can be read as a standalone document.
- **Section 5** provides some concluding remarks on this deliverable.

2 Activities performed towards the next standard version

In the current version (Standard Version 1.0), the activities were focused on the finalization of the Standard Sections that were not fully developed. The activities included various workshops and meetings, data collection from VITALISE project activities like the JRAs and the TAs, the 6th Harmonization Body meeting that took place along with a dedicated session during Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium addressing the VITALISE Harmonization process. This section outlines the activities undertaken to achieve these objectives.

2.1 Living Lab Lexicon Update

As mentioned in the previous Standard D2.6, the work accomplished by the Living Lab Lexicon working group was presented at the Open Living Lab Days 2023 in September 2023 providing a comprehensive account of the term and definition identification process as well as a presentation of a new version of the concept map cited below. Following this presentation, the team continued to collect new terms and definitions capitalizing on important work conducted by ENoLL members working on self-assessment modules and the evaluation framework, as well as searching additional sources on living lab research. We now have more than 60 living lab terms defined, ranging from general living lab terms to terms referring to operations, processes, tools, methods and infrastructure, types of users, impact and values. The work continues with new terms and definitions being placed on the wiki and diverse contexts within which these terms can occur are being explored. This is anticipated to provide variations on basic living lab term definitions based on the specific context within which they are used, e.g. different streams of academia and industry. The Dynamic Living Lab Lexicon continues to grow as a useful resource for Living Lab users and novices. Finally, inspired by the work of the team on the English version of the Living Lab Lexicon, a new team is now being created to begin working on the French version of the Lexicon.

2.2 Filling the Living Lab Business model

A content analysis was conducted by using business model canvas elements as lenses to all the outputs produced during the VITALISE project. The aim of the content analysis was to reveal how the produced outputs are linked to business model elements in order to clarify more in detail the living lab business model. Moreover, the results were compared to initial analysis results which were collected from VITALISE living labs at the beginning of the project grounded on the business model item list by Santonen et al. 2020.

2.3 Activities towards definition of the Living Lab Research and Innovation Phases

As part of reporting on JRA (D5.3, D6.3, D7.3) and TA (D8.2, D9.2, D10.2) case studies, careful evaluation was conducted to identify missing items within the process illustration. Furthermore, additional literature review was undertaken in preparation for a scientific publication on Living Lab as Research Infrastructure. Known research infrastructure characteristics were cross-checked with the process illustration to identify possible gaps.

2.4 Harmonization Board and Body meetings and harmonization outreach

Throughout this last semester iteration, the 6th Harmonization Body meeting was orchestrated, along with the Final Event of the project, “the Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium”, and the Kick-off meeting of the ENoLL Harmonization Working group. The overarching objective was to establish and finalize a unified approach and comprehension of the harmonization activities status, as well as to delineate the forthcoming steps for the completion of the project and the establishment of the Harmonization Working group.

2.4.1 6th Harmonization Body meeting

The 6th Harmonization Body meeting took place during the face-to-face plenary meeting that was held in Madrid between the 27th and 28th of November 2023 (Figure 1). The main scope was initially

to make a debriefing regarding the updates that were included in the Standard version 5 and then to structure the upcoming activities and next steps that would result in the final version of the Standard, Standard version 6, delivered by the end of the project. Lastly, the meeting ended with some remarks about the establishment of the Harmonization working group within ENoLL that was initiated through the VITALISE project and aims to play a crucial role in advancing Living Lab Harmonization efforts and collaboratively establishing a concrete roadmap for the future.

Figure 1 - Snapshots from the 6th Harmonization Body Meeting

2.4.2 Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium

The final event of VITALISE, the “Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium”, was held in Belgium, at Brussels Info Place (BIP) on the 20th of February 2024 (Figure 2), hosting in total around 74 participants.

The symposium was dedicated to the presentation of the outcomes of VITALISE project, with the focus on harmonizing Living Lab services and procedures while recognizing Living Labs as integral Research Infrastructures.

The primary objective of the symposium was a collective reflection with representatives of the European Commission, as well as with relevant stakeholders and beneficiaries of the Research Infrastructures (RIs). The main goal was to discuss and plan the next steps toward a new era where RIs are open and actively involve communities as powerful tools for co-creation. A second objective was to showcase completed or on-going research conducted within the several Living Labs, through oral presentations and pitches.

More specifically, after a warm welcome and introduction by the VITALISE project coordinator, Evdokimos Konstantinidis, and the Scientific coordinator, Panos Bamidis, there was a Keynote about “the role and the importance of RI in Europe” by a representative of EU Commission, Chamberlain Martyn, followed by an introduction on what LLs are and the VITALISE results on the Living Lab Harmonization framework and methodology, presented by Evdokimos Konstantinidis and Despoina Petsani. Then, Dimitri Schuurman from IMEC took the floor for presenting “The importance of Harmonization for a greater impact: the view of the Harmonisation Board and launch of the ENoLL Harmonisation Working Group”. This presentation was followed by Valentina Conotter from SocialIT, highlighting the impact of LLs for external researchers. Afterwards, a roundtable about “the present and future of Living Labs as Research Infrastructures” took place with representatives from the EU Commission, AUTH, McGill University, Licalab and INTRAS, moderated by the Director of ENoLL, Martina Desole, who then continued with a presentation titled “A new generation of researchers ready to exploit LLs for their research”. The next slot was dedicated to the presentations of successful Transnational Access to Living Labs RI by TA representatives from each LL. External researchers who had visited the involved LLs to conduct their own research studies, presented the scope, the methodology and main outcomes of their work. Next in the agenda was Gloria Cea from Universidad

Politécnica de Madrid, who presented the opportunities of Virtual Access to Research Infrastructures, followed by the presentation of Gorka Epelde from VICOMTECH who introduced the VITALISE Digital Tools. This first session of the symposium finished with some remarks and conclusions by the Project coordinator. The following session commenced with an overview of the Joint Research Activity (JRA) Results and the Transnational collaborations carried out under these JRAs. An Open call session dedicated to examples of Living Lab activities in the field of health and well-being was then held, followed by a Panel Discussion about “Unlocking the Cancer R&I Potential: Empowering Communities through Living Labs”. The next Open call session was devoted to presentations on “Living Labs as Research Infrastructures”. Subsequently, another Panel discussion was held, titled “Childhood and Adolescence Health in Living Labs context”, and a final Open call session with presentations on “Live Labs as Research Infrastructures”. The symposium closed warmly with some remarks from the Project coordinator and the anticipation of the next year’s Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium.

Figure 2 - Snapshot from the Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium

2.4.3 Establishment of the Harmonization Working group – Kick-off meeting

Throughout this reporting period, the Harmonization team worked also towards the establishment of the ENoLL Harmonization Working Group (WG). In order to establish the WG as part of the ENoLL network, we prepared the WGs Terms of Reference, explaining the objectives of the WG, the envisaged activities and outcomes, and the proposed structure. We also launched a call inviting Living Labs to participate and 10 members expressed their interest to join the WG. After the official

establishment of the WG, an online kick-off meeting was held on March 22nd 2024 (Figure 3). The VITALISE Harmonization Framework was presented as a starting point for the work of the WG. The participants discussed the objectives of the WG and also planned the next steps.

Figure 3 - Snapshot of the online kick-off meeting of the ENoLL Harmonization Working Group

The discussion revolved around practical validation within the Living Labs network, emphasizing the need to validate frameworks effectively. Participants deliberated on the target audience for such frameworks, exploring whether they should be tailored towards specific groups or be more universal. Additionally, there was a focus on developing guidelines, tools, methods, and standardized terminology to streamline the validation process. Finally, the conversation centred on identifying key pillars and integrating them cohesively into the framework to ensure comprehensive validation across all aspects.

2.4.4 Outreach of the Harmonization Framework

The Living Lab Harmonization Framework received positive reception beyond the VITALISE consortium, with adoption extending into other scientific domains such as soil science and gendered innovation. Six (6) letters of Intent (LoI) were signed declaring their willingness to follow and extend the Living Lab Harmonization Framework. The following organizations/groups provided a LoI that can be found also in the ANNEX.

- Monash University
- Jagiellonian University
- GILL project
- oPEN lab project
- SOILL project
- Open Knowledge Foundation Greece

2.5 Collection of methods and tools

This section includes an updated categorization of the validated questionnaires and tools that are commonly used in Living Labs.

2.5.1 Questionnaires and instruments from the JRAs and the TA research projects

Working towards an update of the first categorization of the tools and questionnaires employed during Joint Research Activities (JRAs) that was included in the previous standard version, all participating Living Labs were assigned with two tasks. The first one was to check and update the information they had initially provided in the Teams Excel spreadsheet about the tools and questionnaires they intended to use in their respective pilots within the JRAs, based on what they actually employed in the performed pilots. The second task was to list in another Excel spreadsheet all the tools and questionnaires that were used by the external researchers during their TA research studies.

Following this data collection, the inputs were once again systematically organized into the four primary axes that were identified in the previous standard version, guided by their purpose and the aspects they measure.

The four main categories are as follows:

1. Health Status & Wellbeing
2. Cognitive Status
3. Physical Activity/Mobility
4. Usability & User Experience Measures

For every questionnaire and tool falling under these axes, the variable measured was identified precisely. The culmination of this effort is encapsulated in the corresponding Part 7C of the Standard, summarizing the tools and the variables measured within each of the aforementioned categories.

2.5.2 Methods and tools analysis of JRA studies

After completion of the JRA case studies, the utilized devices were mapped according to taxonomy classification and examples on measurements and measurement intervals were collected to identify the different data measurement types. In total, 65 devices were used in JRAs case studies (JRA1=22, JRA2=16, JRA3=26) while the number of devices ranged from 1 to 12 between the case studies.

The utilized devices were mapped with taxonomy subcategories. As a result, 46 out of 52 (88 percent) subcategories were addressed in the case studies, thus indicating widespread opportunities to collect digital biomarker data. The following measurement options were detected: 1) Continuous (e.g. 24h monitoring), Pre/Post, Short time duration (e.g. few minutes), Single event, Frequency, Event/Use/Activity duration (e.g. foot contact time, hours of sleep), Change triggered, Relative (e.g. % share of total), Response time, Cross reference to external data (e.g. weather), Sequenced, Amount (e.g. kg, number of steps) and Choice selection.

2.6 Harmonizing the evaluation of living labs

After the collaborative workshops and analysis of the results performed the previous semester (D2.6 Standard Version 5), an iteration of the KPI table was made by the partners of WP 2. This process led to the formulation and classification of 34 general Living Lab KPIs into six main groups. Finally, these results were presented again to the diverse groups of Living Lab stakeholders during online presentations.

The Table 1 provides an overview of the 34 developed and validated general Living Lab KPIs.

Table 1 - General Living Lab KPIs

Chapter	Criterion	KPI
Strategy	Governance	1. % of (active) involvement of a balanced and diverse group of stakeholders in the development of the vision & mission of the living lab (e.g., all Q4 represented is 100%)
		2. % of participation of a balanced and diverse group of stakeholders in the governance of the living lab (strategic & operational roles and decision-making processes)

		3. Presence of partner agreements/arrangements for co-innovation	
		4. Completeness of a strategic roadmap for the living lab (SMART goals, responsibilities, and decision-making processes)	
	Business Model	5. Completeness of the described business model approach (value propositions, problems & solutions, activities & resources, key stakeholders, customers, users, costs & revenues, metrics & impacts)	
		6. Number of (different) services offered by the living lab (e.g., stakeholder engagement) covering (all) different phases of the innovation cycle	
	Culture & Collaboration	7. Presence of internal & external business & client relation management process/strategy (including contracts)	
		8. Frequency of internal communication & results sharing to keep partners informed & aligned	
		9. Number of regional, national & international collaborations beyond the scope of an individual living lab project	
	Operations	Human Resources	10. % of Implementation of needed internal roles and responsibilities within the operational living lab team in a flexible way (are all roles sufficiently attributed depending on the size of the operational living lab team)
		Operations	11. Time spent within successfully completed projects and/or activities related to the living lab (how many weeks/months/years of experience does the living lab has in running projects and/or activities)
12. Completeness & frequency of internal self-monitoring processes (how often is the living lab monitoring essential parts of their organization: strategic, financial, equipment & infrastructure, policy, project outcomes)			
Equipment & infrastructure		13. % accessibility in time to facilities (e.g., offices, co-creation spaces, testing facilities...)	
		14. % accessibility in time to hard- & software (e.g., co-creation materials, computers, wearables, interaction software, polling/survey software...)	
Openness		Innovation partnerships, projects & processes	15. % of implementation needed processes to safeguard a reflective and iterative approach to transdisciplinary collaboration
	16. % of implementation of needed processes to safeguard an ethical approach (e.g., regulatory requirements, data protection needed, etc.)		
	Ownership of results	17. % of implementation of needed rules & regulations regarding the use, sharing & licensing of data and IP of collaborative outcomes	

		18. % of implementation of user agreements (data, IPR, rights, liabilities)
Users reality	User centricity	19. % of diversity of stakeholders involved as end-users in living lab projects and/or activities
		20. Degree of influence end-users exerts on the different phases of the innovation cycle (from informing to empowerment)
	Lifecycle real-life	21. Degree of involvement of end-users in the different phases of the innovation cycle e.g., problem space, solution space, implementation space...)
		22. Degree of use of real-life contexts of users in the different phases of the innovation cycle
Tools methods	23. Degree of appropriateness of tools & methods used for the different phases of the innovation cycle	
	24. Frequency of external communication & results sharing to keep end-users and external stakeholders informed and engaged	
Impact value	Co-created values	25. % Satisfaction of users/stakeholders (from the whole value chain) concerning their involvement/influence on the innovation cycle
		26. Number of relevant (open) educational resources (including datasets, trainings) shared/provided for relevant stakeholders
		27. % Satisfaction of users/stakeholders concerning knowledge sharing & capacity building (learning materials & infrastructures)
	Impacts	28. Completeness & frequency of impact assessments (how often is the living lab monitoring different types of impacts they are generating: societal, environmental, economic, regulatory, academic)
Stability & harmonization	Stability	29. % Increase in number of relationships (with a reliable partner network and customers)
		30. Level of financial sustainability based on a balanced & diversified set of fundings (structural vs. project-based) & revenue streams
		31. Number of living lab value propositions, flexible to adapt to new circumstances
	Harmonization & scale-up	32. % Increase in number of partners committed to scale up products/solutions/services developed by the living lab
33. Number of products/solutions/services (able to be) scaled-up		

		<p>34. Number of participation in (cross-border/cross-sectoral) initiatives/projects based on harmonized living lab infrastructures, standards, skills, methods, tools processes or services</p>
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Development of a self-assessment tool for Living Labs

Based on the 34 general Living Lab KPIs, the partners of Work Package 2 developed a set of quantitative questions to collect data around the KPIs in a user-friendly way via an online self-assessment tool.

In October 2023, an online validation survey was set up to collect feedback on:

- the comprehensibility of the proposed questions,
- the difficulties to answer the proposed questions.

Figure 4 below provides a screenshot of this online validation survey.

Figure 4 - Screenshot validation survey questions self-assessment tool

In total, 46 different stakeholders (ENoLL and Forum LLSA members, Living Labs from EU funded projects, academic Living Lab experts and ENoLL executive board members) participated in this survey and provided additional feedback on the questions and answering possibilities. This feedback from the stakeholders was analysed and integrated into the final set of self-assessment questions by the partners of Work Package 2.

3 Updates on the Standard

This Section summarizes the updates that were made in this final Standard Version between M31-M36 of the VITALISE project regarding the Harmonization activities. As previously mentioned, although the deliverable is entitled “Standard Version 6”, it is the final version of the Standard and the authors of this document decided that the specific standard should actually be Version 1.0 as it is the first version that includes all the initially defined parts.

Updates are included in Part 1, the LLL, concluding in a final set of terms and definitions, as well as in Part 2, with the finalization of Business Model chapters and updates on Living Lab Governance – Research and Innovation Process Map. This Section also includes the final version of the Living Lab KPIs. Furthermore, updates were applied to Part 7 Living Lab methods and tools with the final categorization of Living Lab validated questionnaires and tools. For this Deliverable, the objectives that were defined along with the related project activities are presented in Table 2.

Table 2 - Objectives with the related project activities presentation

Standard and delivery date	Objective	Related project activities
Standard Version 6 – March 2024 [M36]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Finalization Business Model chapters Updates in new terms of the LLL Updates on Living Lab Governance – Research and Innovation Process Map Final version of the KPIs Updates on Methods and tools - questionnaires and instruments from the JRAs and the TA research studies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> LL Research Infrastructures available in EOSC marketplace Final deliverables on JRAs and TAs Need for final harmonized evaluation criteria of the LLs Finalization of the JRAs Finalization of the TAs

3.1 PART 1 Living Lab Lexicon

The following graph (Figure 5) is the updated version of the concept map. All the changes and modifications from the previous version have been marked in blue. In this final Standard version (1.0), we include also a table with the final set of thirty (30) terms and definitions.

Figure 5 - Current Concept Map

3.2 PART 2 Living Lab Governance and Business Model

The updates, introduced on this part, are coming from the results produced by the analysis of the VITALISE Harmonization Body members, resulting in a definition of the Living Lab Business Model Value proposition, as well as the Analysis of the Living Lab Key Performance Indicators that is part of the Living Lab Governance.

3.2.1 Living Lab Business Model

This Standard Version includes all the updated information for the Business Model section, namely partner networks, channels, customer relationships, cost structure and revenue streams. The value proposition section was also updated with an additional table that presents the key elements of the LL value proposition. The key activities section of the Business Model is linked to the Services Section of the Standard, as the key activities are actually referred to the defined Living Lab services. The table presenting the Services categorization, inputs and outputs was also updated based on the Business Model analysis.

3.2.2 Living Lab Governance – Key Performance Indicators

The Standard Version 1.0 presents the updated set of KPIs. This new set is the first stable version of the KPIs that is currently used into the certification process of ENoLL to assess incoming applications for membership of the network and the benchmarking process of ENoLL. It is also used as a self-assessment tool for the Living Labs within Water-Mining project, Rewaise project and oPEN Lab project.

3.2.3 Living Lab Governance – Research and Innovation Process Map

Figure 6 presents an updated version of the logical relationships between different Living Lab R&D-, back-office and Auxiliary services, as well as Living Lab key asset repositories. The updated version was created as a result of the evaluating JRA and TA case studies.

Figure 6 - Current version of the Living Lab Research and Innovation process map

The current version includes following updates:

Color coding: In the illustration, the following color coding is added and used: White boxes are referring to R&D-services where living lab is in direct contact with its customers. Grey color boxes indicate that the service is back-office services, having more administrative and R&D support function. Auxiliary services indicated with hexagon are auxiliary processes interlink with living lab activities.

Touch points

- **Access option:** The following three access options were added: 1) Excellence-driven access mode where access is granted on the basis of the peer-reviewed scientific excellence, 2) Market-driven access mode includes a fee and therefore outcome of the study may remain confidential, and 3) Wide access meaning offering as open access as possible without peer-review or monetary fee requirement.

Customer acquisition

- **Desk/market research:** Location in the illustration was changed between customer acquisition and detailed project planning to highlight its nature in these two different situations.
- **Maintenance:** Living lab facilities and equipment require maintenance such as software updates.

Detailed project planning

- **Desk/market research:** Location in the illustration was changed between customer acquisition and detailed project planning to highlight its nature in these two different situations.
- **Resource allocation:** Includes evaluating the availability of human, technical and facility resources in order to determine the best persons, equipment and facilities for the project.

Project implementation and dissemination

- **IPR management:** Location of the IPR management was changed between customer acquisition and detailed project planning to highlight its nature in these two different situations. Furthermore,

link to contract / consortium agreement was added, since many times for example existing IPR issues are already defined there.

- **Quality and Risk management:** Risk management was added together with quality management. Risk management identify, analyse and prioritize project and operational risks to minimize or prevent the probability or impact of unfortunate event.
- **Research, Development and Innovation (RDI) process and services:** Title was changed to better highlight the nature of these three different processes. Additionally, arrows were added to the LL service portfolio to highlight service selection within each phase.
- **Permanent and Ad Hoc panels:** Modification was made by separating Ad hoc and permanent panel. Ad hoc user panel is established for a specific short-term period for a project or an event activity and is terminated afterwards. On the contrary, permanent panel consist pre-recruited panel members who are filling their profile information based on common template and indicate their willingness to participate in forthcoming living lab activities. At the time of registration, participants do not know exactly what is the activity and when they are needed. Permanent panels are used for smooth and faster user recruitment.
- **FAIR data compliance process:** Data is FAIR if it meets principles of Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability (FAIR). This process ensures that all, or part of, the data that a project has generated will qualify as FAIR data.
- **FAIR data and Closed data repositories:** Data repository was divided into FAIR and Closed data repositories where the first one provides access to external users and the latter ones have restricted access. Link between the two open data repositories was added to highlight that these two repositories are the same.

3.3 PART 7 Data Collection Approaches

In version (1.0), the update in Part 7, concerns only Part 7C, concretely the categorization tables for questionnaires and instruments used in VITALISE JRAs, including also those used during the TA research studies.

3.3.1 PART 7C. Validated questionnaires and instrument

In Part 7C of Section 4 within the Standard version of this deliverable, we have included the tables that present the updated categorization of the questionnaires and instruments from the JRAs and the Tas. This Part serves as a means to provide a comprehensive overview of all the instruments and questionnaires utilized throughout the VITALISE JRAs and the TA research studies, along with the measured variables.

4 Standard Version 0.4

This Section is the sixth (v.0.6) public version of Living Labs Standard. Although the deliverable is entitled “Standard Version 6”, it is the final version of the Standard released by the end of the project on M36 and the authors of this document decided that the specific standard should actually be Version 1.0 as it is the first version that includes all the previously defined parts. This Section is structured in such a way so that it can be separated from the rest of the deliverable and published in the VITALISE wiki page as a standalone document.

4.1 Introduction

The European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) – an international non-profit association promoting and enhancing user-driven innovation ecosystem defines living lab is *“a user-centred, open innovation ecosystems based on systematic user co-creation approach, integrating research and innovation processes in real life communities and settings”* (<https://enoll.org/about-us/>).

This wiki serves as an open space for the public review of the harmonization version and encourages open discussion about the various items that are presented. The information presented in this wiki will be updated every six months and published after approval from the governance Board and Body of the Harmonization process. In each section you can find when and by which each version is approved (e.g., “Approved by the VITALISE H2020 Living Labs' consensus report on XX/XX/XXXX”.)

The VITALISE Harmonization process is governed by two main groups, the VITALISE Harmonization Body and the VITALISE Harmonization Board. By VITALISE Harmonization Body we refer to a wider community of stakeholders consisting of Living Lab researchers and practitioners, healthcare professionals, policy makers and professionals that are interested in research performed in Living Lab infrastructures. VITALISE Harmonization Board aims to co-ordinate the Harmonization procedures and practices and consists of representatives of each Living Lab in the consortium, as well as independent representatives from the Health and Wellbeing domain and policy makers. Representatives of other Health and Wellbeing Living Labs are also encouraged to join. This board will take decisions regarding the Standard Versions.

The aim of this Living Lab standard is to guide Living Lab operators and researchers to execute, develop and maintain a harmonized framework for systematic Living Lab practices. It is not a rigid and strict representation of what Living Labs are doing but it rather be used as guidelines towards the identification of common approaches. Living Labs are structures that encourage serendipity in the way that they are working and should be handled as such. The standard versions concern mainly the LLs but they also borrow knowledge, expertise and experience from various other domains, like open science, citizen science, open innovation, innovation management, responsible research and innovation, etc., on a sharing basis. Within this framework, there are several tools and methodologies exploited in LLs which could also be applied in several other research contexts.

By Establishing Living Lab management system, the Living Labs will:

1. Promote the expansion and growth of Living Lab movement beyond current actors and customers,
2. Stimulate cross-organization and transnational research collaboration,
3. Enable data sharing and comparison of the research results,
4. Increase research quality, and
5. Define a common terminology and language among researchers and practitioners.

The Figure 7 defines the conceptual overview of the living lab management system presented in this standard document.

Figure 7 - The key elements and conceptual overview of the living lab management system

The following key elements will concern the Living Lab community and will be further assessed in the next Standard Version that will be updated by the ENoLL Harmonization WG.

1. Living Lab Lexicon (LLL) – terms and definitions: LLL introduces, lists and shortly defines a comprehensive catalogue of terms associated and included in different parts of the living lab standard (i.e., 2 to 9). The LLL is grounded on Wikipedia type of user interface, where definitions including overlapping terminology, will enable quick jumping between different descriptions and to in-depth descriptions in other standard sections. LLL will help to discuss living lab related issues among the different stakeholder, who currently are using varying terminology.

2. Living Lab Governance and Business Model: This Living Lab Harmonization Section consists of two parts: The Living Lab Business Model (LLBM) and the Living Lab Governance Model.

- “A business model describes the rationale of how an organization creates, delivers, and captures value” (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010). LLBM part is grounded on Business Model Canvas (BMC) approach (Ibid.), which consists of the following nine different elements. (1) key activities, (2) key resources, (3) partner network, (4) value proposition, (5) customer segments, (6) channels, (7) customer relationships, (8) cost structure and (9) revenue streams. The purpose of the LLBM part is to identify different attributes associated with each nine BMC element. Having a unified way to describe LLBM enables quantitative business model comparison between different living labs as well as open ups possibilities to track changes in business model strategies.

- A governance model for Living Labs is a framework or set of principles that guide how a Living Lab operates, makes decisions, and manages its activities. It defines the rules, roles, responsibilities, and processes that ensure effective and efficient functioning of the Living Lab. The Living Lab Governance model of this Standard is underpinned by the identified Key Performance Indicators of Living Labs that cover all the aspects of Living Lab activities and functioning in a comprehensive framework.

3. Research process: The part ‘Living Lab research process’ focuses on defining the key steps to execute and define a living lab research methodology. The part is comprised of (1) a common template to define research protocol, (2) ethical and data management plans, (3) participant recruitment procedures, (4) infrastructure selection procedure, (5) data collection procedures, (6)

data analysis and comparison practices and (7) fair data practices for opening data. Each phase consists of aim, outcome and maturity level description. Furthermore, research process phases are interlinked with other living lab standard parts in order to identify which other items are relevant for each research process phase. Having a standard way to describe living lab research design helps developing a unified research methodology, which enables a robust results comparison across different studies, increasing the research quality.

4. Innovation process: Living Lab innovation process part focuses on defining in an unambiguous way, the different innovation management process phases which are or can be covered during the living lab data collection phase. This part defines an iterative and agile user-centred innovation and design process, and align the phases with Technology Readiness Level (TRL) concept. TRL is a widely adopted concept to describe developed solution maturity level. Respectively to research process, different innovation process phases are interlinked with other Living Lab standard parts in order to identify which of the other items are relevant for each process phase.

5. R&D services: R&D services refer to a group of common R&D services, which a Living Lab can offer to its customers during the different Living Lab R&D process phases. Each service combines one or more data collection approaches or other activities or parts of the Living Lab standard, needed to accomplish living lab R&D project as whole or part of it. Each service description defines the type of service and additional details related to service delivery such as technical and functional quality. In the long run, the aim is to define the Minimum Acceptable Service Level for each service type in order to ensure service quality across the different Living Labs.

6. Data collection approaches. Data collection approaches consist of the following three sub-parts: (1) methods and tools, (2) devices and technologies and (3) validated questionnaires and instruments. This part provides a collection of practical data collection approaches, which can be combined in multiple variations when defining a living lab project research methodology.

6A Methods and tools part identifies and describes the different types of specific research methods, tools, and practices, which can be used for data collection during a living lab project. Among these are e.g., interviews, workshops and surveys. In the future, the standard will be used for sharing the best practices and defining the appropriate ways to utilize the particular method in different living research contexts.

6B Devices and technologies defines commonly used technological solutions to collect and analyse living lab research data. Correspondingly to 7A methods and devices, the standard will be used for sharing the best practices and defining the appropriate ways to utilize the particular technology in a research setting.

6C. Validated questionnaires and instrument consists of numerous scientifically validated surveys, scales, interventions or similar, known to be reliable measure-certain phenomenon. The Standard will especially promote questionnaires and instruments which are multilingual and freely available.

7. Living lab Research Infrastructure (RI): This part provides a classification schema and definitions for different types of Living Lab infrastructures. In regulation No 1291/2013, European Union Parliament and Council of the European Union (2013) defines RIs as “facilities, resources and services that are used by the research communities to conduct research and foster innovation in their fields”. The definitions and descriptions for (1) single-sited, (2) distributed, (3) virtual and (4) mobile living lab facilities are provided.

To conclude, it is important to clarify that the above-described conceptual overview and the included key elements of the living lab management system are preliminary concepts. Therefore, the names, details and concept itself can be changed in the following versions.

4.2 Scope of this document

This is the final version of the Health and Wellbeing Living Labs Standard (Version 1.0). The structure and the content of all the previous Standard versions released every six months was continuously updated and improved to reach this final Standard (Version 1.0) that is now released with the end of the project on M36. The authors of this document decided that this specific Standard should actually

be Version 1.0, instead of Version 6, as it is the first version that includes all the required parts. The information presented is a result of an analysis performed in the VITALISE project and more details about the analysis can be found in the Deliverables of the project.

The rest of the document presents:

- **PART 1 Living Lab Lexicon (LLL):** Collection of terms that are widely used in Living Lab performed activities.
- **PART 2. Living lab governance and business model:** The identified value proposition, the Living Lab KPIs and the Research and Innovation process map.
- **PART 3. Research process:** presenting the Living Lab research phases.
- **PART 4. Innovation process:** presenting the Living Lab Innovation phases.
- **PART 5. R&D Services:** A list of R&D services provided by Health and Wellbeing Living Labs.
- **PART 6. Living lab research infrastructure:** a first categorization of existing Living Lab infrastructures.
- **PART 7A. Methods and tools:** In this standard version we included the identified tools that support ethics applications.
- **PART 7B. Devices and technologies:** In this standard version identified devices and technologies are presented as a part of R&D service descriptions.
- **PART 7C. Validated questionnaires and instruments** contains a first categorization of the questionnaires and instruments that are used in Living Labs for performing research studies.

4.3 PART 1. Living Lab Lexicon (LLL)

Working within the context of the Horizon Virtual Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure (VITALISE) project, and to harmonize processes, procedures and tools across the European Living Labs including some Canadian Living Labs, we began the creation of the Living Lab Lexicon (LLL). The goal is to establish a common language to facilitate and increase understanding and communication between the different ‘players’ within the Living Lab (LL) communities and all those who come in contact with Living Labs. The Living Lab Lexicon (LLL) is dynamic, with key living lab terms being identified, defined, and shared with the LL community and beyond. We are mindful of the fact that certain terms have variations in meaning depending on the context in which they are used.

A team of VITALISE researchers from European and Canadian LLs, supported by external experts in the fields of linguistics and psycholinguistics, as well as by a medical librarian, was assembled. The general objectives of the initiative are: 1) Determine and select which LL terms to define. 2) Identify already existing definitions for selected terms. Consider who the target audience(s) is (are). 4) Propose definitions for the terms selected within a framework representing the LL process and reality.

Following a rigorous and iterative process of term selection and identification of definitions, a first set of terms and definitions are presented here. This list will continue to be populated as more terms are identified and defined. We also present a first concept map containing some of the terms and definitions (see Table 3).

Table 3 - Living Lab Lexicon: Terms and Definitions

Living Lab	Living Labs are real-life test and experimentation environments that foster co-creation and open innovation among the main actors of the Quadruple Helix Model
Co-creation	The collaborative process of creating new value for and with all the relevant stakeholders. In LL, values are bottom-up co-created not only for but also by all relevant stakeholders, ensuring a higher adoption at the end.

Open innovation	The practice of businesses and organizations sourcing ideas from external sources as well as internal ones. This means sharing knowledge and information about problems and looking to people outside the business or organization for solutions and suggestions.
Innovation readiness level	The model assesses the idea development on a scale from 1 to 9 in six key areas of innovation development. For each area, clear definitions of the different levels are given as well as milestones and activities that are needed to reach each level. The model is a highly useful tool for teams developing ideas and coaches or managers supporting idea development to measure progress and status.
Technology readiness level (TRL)	<p>A method for estimating the maturity of technologies during the acquisition phase of a program. TRLs enable consistent and uniform discussions of technical maturity across different types of technology.</p> <p>TRL1: Basic principles observed</p> <p>TRL2: Technology concept formulated</p> <p>TRL3: Experimental proof of concept</p> <p>TRL4: Technology validated in lab</p> <p>TRL5: Technology validated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)</p> <p>TRL6: Technology demonstrated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)</p> <p>TRL7: System prototype demonstration in operational environment</p> <p>TRL8: System complete and qualified</p> <p>TRL9: Actual system proven in operational environment (competitive manufacturing in the case of key enabling technologies; or in space)</p>
Multi-stakeholder participation	Taking a holistic view on society, involving stakeholders from the quadruple helix model
The Quadruple Helix Model	The Quadruple Helix Model of innovation recognizes four major actors in the innovation system: science / academia (education & research); public sector / policy; industry / private sector; and society /citizens.
Stakeholder involvement / engagement	The process of stakeholder involvement / engagement is voluntary, open, and active dialog, which identifies the current position of all parties included, outlines objectives and outcomes and identifies how to achieve them. Parties that are included in the engagement can change but the process of engagement continues.
Lead-user	They are the 'leading edge', well qualified and motivated to make significant contributions to the development of new products and services. Lead users face new needs of the market and this significantly earlier than the majority of the customers in a market segment. They will profit strongly from innovations that provide a solution for those needs. Lead users do not just experience any new need, but those needs that most customers will face in the future.

End-user	The term "end user" refers to the consumer of a good or service, often who has some innate know-how that is unique to consumers. End user experience and support are crucial for the success of user-oriented products and services.
Customer	LL perspective: An entity (individual, private or public organization, or company) that pays a LL to perform services (co-creation/research) and pays for the results of those services Stakeholder perspective: An entity who pays for the end-product of the co-creation/research (results) within the general context of the "market"
Expert	An expert is somebody who has a broad and deep understanding and competence in terms of knowledge, skill and experience through practice and education in a particular field. Informally, an expert is someone widely recognized as a reliable source of technique or skill whose faculty for judging or deciding rightly, justly, or wisely is accorded authority and status by peers or the public in a specific well-distinguished domain. An expert, more generally, is a person with extensive knowledge or ability based on research, experience, or occupation and in a particular area of study. Experts are called in for advice on their respective subject, but they do not always agree on the particulars of a field of study. An expert can be believed, by virtue of credentials, training, education, profession, publication or experience, to have special knowledge of a subject beyond that of the average person, sufficient that others may officially (and legally) rely upon the individual's opinion on that topic.
Non-user	A potential user or a group of people who are not using the LL services, persons who may be interested but not using yet. They are customers and experts who are not currently using the LL services but could. Could be users who used the services in the past but no longer do.
Panel	Panel is pre-existing group of pre-screened people (e.g. patients, practitioners etc.) who have given their consent to take part in different research activities over an agreed period. Panel members have given their contact details and other profiling information, which enables fast recruitment for specific
Living Lab services	Services offered by a living lab. These can include the following: Project planning and management, Market and competitor intelligence services, Co-creating products, services and processes, Testing and validation services, Access to data, Capacity building, Co-creation workshops, Competitor and market analysis and benchmarking, Concept and proof-of-concept tests- feasibility studies, Grant writing and funding application support services, Hackathon and design sprints, Interviews and focus groups, Large-scale real-life testing and piloting, Legal, regulation and safety standard support, Small-scale real life testing and experimentation.

Project planning and management	May start with briefing session where a potential customer presents their research and development needs and describe the current status of their solution. Based on briefing, a project plan is made. The plan describes the set of methods and approaches to be used for data collection during the planned project activities in set time frame. User engagement plan contains a description of targeted end-users (and other relevant key stakeholders) as well as a description of the real-life or simulated environments where living lab process will take place. The possibilities of operating in real-life environments and engaging the targeted end-users and other relevant stakeholders in project planned activities, are closely intertwined with the opportunities offered by the local innovation network.
Market and competitor intelligence services	Data and insight collection relating to future trends, competitors, similar products and services by using secondary research methods i.e. making synthesis on the basis of existing research, reports, documents, marketing materials etc. The aim is to identify a suitable target market give an estimation about the size of the demand in the market as well as understating the current and future restrictions.
Co-creating products, services and processes	Various research and co-creation methods, and tools to facilitate the collaborative and iterative development efforts during the different innovation process phases (e.g. observations, shadowing, diary studies, ethnographic studies, interviews, surveys, user personas, customer journey, workshops, hackathons and design sprints). These services include collaboration and interaction with various end-users and other relevant stakeholder. Expert opinions, sparring and advisory services are also commonly used approaches.
Testing and validation services	Can use the same methods and approaches as the co-creation phases. However, the aim is to test the developed solution attractiveness among the end-users and test if the solutions really can be made. Testing methods includes test for (1) selecting and ranking ideas, (2) making feasibility and proof-of-concept tests, (3) doing simulations, testing usability and prototypes, (4) running small- and large-scale tests in real life environments to experiment and pilot test, (5) making impact assessments, validation test, clinical trials and regulatory approval tests and, finally (6) tracking the solution market performance and collecting for further development.
Access to data	Referring to a service that enables customers to access or retrieve data from one or more database consisting relevant data, which can be used for development or testing purposes.
Capacity building	Offering training for end-users and/or practitioners to improve their skills and knowledge about living lab approach, co-creation, iterative development and healthcare and wellbeing market. Stimulating knowledge sharing and awareness raising by publishing professional and scientific publications and arranging events, site visits and seminars.

Co-creation workshops	Workshop is a facilitated a group activity to find solutions for a specific problem by gathering ideas, solutions and insights from workshop participants while using variety of methods. Depending on the workshop focus, it may comprise ideation, concept development and testing.
Competitor and market analysis and benchmarking	Quantitative and qualitative methods are used to evaluate the size of the market both, in volume and in value. Customer segments, buying patterns, competition, and the economic environment are defined to identify the regulations and the barriers to entry. Defining the market by listing and describing current, future, direct and indirect competitors and analysing their competitive offering (e.g. SWOT) and user experience. Comparing offerings by measuring the performance of the developed products, services, or processes against those, which are considered to be the best in the industry. Can also consist of literature reviews to search and evaluate the available scientific or professional body of knowledge for the given subject or chosen topic area.
Concept and proof-of-concept tests-feasibility studies	<p>Concept test is low cost and quick process in which high-level concept(s) is tested with real end-users via different methods such as interviews and surveys.</p> <p>In order to conduct concept test, preliminary concept description must exists in written or visual format, which is then communicated to the real end-users or experts. The main aim is to collect feedback for the initial concept proposal and its possible variations. Concept test can also include a feasibility study, which covers technical, economic, legal, operational and scheduling issues relating the proposed concept. In all, concept-testing phase verifies if a concept has market interest, while feasibility study shows if the product or service on the basis of concept can be developed. Collected feedback includes also improvement suggestions.</p>
Grant writing and funding application support services	Offering tailored support by identifying the proper local, regional, national and international funding instruments, helping to write and manage a funding application process including finding the right partners for the project, if needed.
Hackathon and design sprints	Typically, 2–5-day event in which group of people will develop a solution to the predefined challenge by using a variety of co-creation methods. The outcome of the co-creation activity (i.e. the solution) can range from low-fidelity to hi-fidelity prototypes, mock-ups or written concept description for a product or service.
Interviews and focus groups,	<p>Interview is a qualitative research technique in which intensive face-to-face, phone or web-meeting interview is conducted with a small number of individual respondents to explore their perspectives on a particular topic. A focus group is a qualitative research method in which a trained moderator conducts a collective interview and make sure that the discussions focuses on the research questions.</p> <p>Typically focus group consist 6 to 8 participants who represent a sample of an end-user target group. The aim is to capture target group</p>

	in-depth knowledge concerning experiences, attitudes, perceptions, beliefs and opinions regarding research question(s).
Large-scale real-life testing and piloting	Similar to small-scale testing but longer in duration or with a larger number of test participants who are representing the real end-users of the target group. During piloting, the aim is to evaluate the full scale and fully functional product(s) or service(s) at the system level in a real environment with real end-users to make sure that the solution is scalable.
Legal, regulation and safety standard support	Providing support to navigate in the legal, regulatory and safety standard requirements and help with planning to meet requirements.
Small-scale real-life testing and experimentation	An experiment is a small scale and short-term preliminary study conducted to evaluate feasibility of the suggested product or service and to improve it based on the testing result. Testing includes a small number of test participants who are representing the real end-users of the target group.

Current Concept Map

Figure 8 - Living Lab Lexicon: Concept Map

4.4 PART 2. Living Lab Business and Governance Model

“A business model describes the rationale of how an organization creates, delivers, and captures value” (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010). LLBM part is grounded on Business Model Canvas (BMC) approach (Ibid.), which consists of the following nine different elements. (1) key activities, (2) key resources, (3) partner network, (4) value proposition, (5) customer segments, (6) channels, (7) customer relationships, (8) cost structure and (9) revenue streams. The living lab standard defines common attributes associated with each nine BMC element.

4.4.1 Key activities

Key activities: In the context of living labs, our observations and content analysis revealed that all key activities appear to be significantly linked to living lab services. Therefore, instead of speaking about key activities, it is suggested that living lab services is to be a better way to communicate living lab activities. The following two different approaches were identified to classify services: First, classification based on living lab processes including 1) customer acquisition, 2) detailed project planning and 3) project implementation and dissemination processes as presented in Table 18 in section 4.7. *Second*, classification to 1) R&D-services including activities directly supporting collaborative generation of new knowledge, 2) Back-office services including all administrative and R&D support functions, and 3) Auxiliary services including auxiliary processes interlink with living R&D- or back-office services. A template listing living lab services and mapping them to classification frameworks is presented in Table 18.

4.4.2 Key resources

Living lab key resources includes following:

Table 4 - Living Lab Key Resources

Funding from project	Grants, fixed funding, investments, and revenues generated from services.
Living lab personnel	1) Living lab personnel including living lab manager, project manager, panel manager, facilitators and researchers, 2) Living lab hosting organization additional human resources e.g. administration and legal teams, teachers, management team, students who receive salary
Living lab research infrastructure and technologies	1) Physical facilities and campuses, 2) Laboratories and simulations environments, 3) Technological devices and tools, 4) Virtual environments, 5) IT infrastructure. To specify the types of devices living labs have, "Categorizing digital data collection and intervention tools in health and wellbeing living lab settings: A modified Delphi study" was finalized and published in the International Journal of Medical Informatics. The PaneLab (https://app.thepanelab.com/) was also developed during VITALISE. It can be used for managing contacts and to describe and market living lab researcher infrastructure.
Partners as defined in partners section	See partners section description
End-user and patient panels	Access to patients and customers wide range with different diagnosis, living conditions, functionality or similar
Non-paid volunteers	1) Bachelor, master or PhD level students or researchers who gain study credits instead of salary, participation is based on educational purpose instead earning a living, 2) Other volunteers having a formal contract
Data and publication databases	1) Open and closed access databases such as health care data infrastructure or living lab own data generated in projects, 2) Access to scientific publication databases
Subcontracted experts	1) Consultants, 2) health care professionals and high level medical personnel, 3) business managers, or similar
Living lab IPR portfolio	Patents and trademarks
Standardized processes	1) VITALISE harmonized processes, 2) ISO certified for software production

4.4.3 Partner network

The partner analysis conducted at the beginning of the project didn't reveal any major updates to the key partner list for health and wellbeing living labs. However, since the partners were health and wellbeing-related, the list cannot be directly utilized in other thematic living lab domains. A framework presented in Table 5, including quadruple helix actors as columns and geographical focus as rows, is suggested as a universal tool to classify living lab partnerships.

Table 5 - Living lab partner classification tool

	Academia / Education / Research	Public sector / Policy	Industry / Private sector	Civil society
Local partners: Collaboration partnerships within a one city or municipal or smaller geographical areas such as neighbourhood or city district.				
Regional partners: Collaboration partnerships within a province, a region, or a state which goes beyond single city or municipal, but geographical area is not covering an entire country (e.g. Flanders, Catalunya or Helsinki capital region).				
National partners: Collaboration partnerships at the level of an entire country.				
International and transnational partners: Collaboration partnerships beyond border of one country.				

Table 6 presents examples for health and wellbeing living labs.

Table 6 - Health and wellbeing living lab partner examples

Research organizations	1) Research institutions, 2) Universities, 3) National research centers and institutes, 4) Research councils, 5) Individual research experts, 6) State research institute; 7) Public Research and Technology Organization (RTOs) and 8) Government research agencies
Educational organizations	Educational institutions such as 1) Early childhood education and care; 2) School education; 3) Higher education; 4) Vocational training and 5) Adult learning. Individual students and teachers
Regional organizations public	1) Regional support and administrative departments, 2) Regional council, 3) Regional government
Health care organizations: Primary, Secondary, tertiary care organizations and units	1) Health professional organizations who act as a first point of consultation for all patients within the healthcare system, 2) Health services provided by medical specialists and other health professionals for inpatients on referral from a primary health professionals, 3) Specialized higher level consultative health care within the hospital, usually for inpatients and on referral from a primary or secondary health professional.
Municipals and cities	Various administrative and development departments

Networks and clusters	1) Company clusters and company networks, 2) industry expert groups, 3) International network organizations such ECHAlliance, European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL), The European Innovation Partnership on Active and Healthy Ageing (EIP on AHA), ACTIVAGE IoT Ecosystem, 4) Life science cluster, 5) Business accelerator networks, 6) Scientific communities
State level organizations	State budgetary unit, Health data authority, Ministry of education
Private company	1) E-health, M-health, and digital service providers and development companies, 2) tangible equipment and device manufactures, 3) medical devices and equipment providers, 4) pharma companies, 5) local SMEs
Preventive healthcare, wellbeing and wellness service providers. Private and public institutions for social care and wellbeing	Organizations who provide services for the wellbeing of citizens such as 1) Fitness centres and gyms, 2) coaching and personal training, 3) spa and beauty services, 4) physiotherapy, 5) cultural houses, 6) community centres.
NGOs, NPOs, third sector organizations and unorganized citizen groups	‘Value-driven’ organizations promoting, supporting or serving specific objective(s) or causes including such as patients associations, senior associations

4.4.4 Value proposition

Living lab key value proposition elements are described in Table 7. Based on that we have formulated the examples for various stakeholders of the quadruple helix.

Table 7 - Living lab value proposition elements

Enhanced collaboration and networking possibilities	Opening collaboration and networking possibilities which otherwise would be impossible or hard to gain.
Validity and reliability	Stability and truthfulness of living lab process outputs.
Improved innovation	All the different aspects in which the developed solution, whether it be a product, service, process, decision, policy, etc., becomes better due living lab process.
Financial and process benefits	The gains that can be expressed in financial terms resulting from the living lab innovation process or the improvement of the developed solution.
Benefits for users and society	The impact of living lab process outcome to users and society.
Increased skills and capabilities	Improved ability of a person, group, organization, or system to meet its objectives or perform better due living lab process outcome.
Safe environment for RDI	Ensuring regulatory and legal compliance, as well as a risk-free area for experimentation, where innovations can be developed and tested

Value proposition for companies:

Living Labs provide a compelling opportunity for companies to connect with users and actively involve them throughout various phases of the innovation process. This inclusive approach enables companies to effectively test, validate, and analyze the impact of their solutions iteratively. Moreover, by participating in Living Labs, companies gain access to enhanced networking and collaboration opportunities, fostering a dynamic ecosystem for innovation and growth.

Value proposition for policy makers and public authorities:

Living Labs present an effective platform for policy makers and public authorities to identify, engage, and involve users and diverse stakeholders throughout various phases of the innovation process. Through this collaborative approach, Living Labs facilitate the gathering of reliable feedback, needs, and requirements from the real end-users. Additionally, the process allows for the verification of user acceptance, ensuring that policies and public initiatives are designed and implemented with a strong focus on meeting the genuine needs of the community they serve.

Value proposition for researchers:

Living Labs provide researchers with unparalleled networking and collaboration opportunities, fostering a rich environment for academic and practical exchange. Beyond this, Living Labs serve as a powerful platform for researchers to create and demonstrate proof of concept, enabling them to test and validate their research results iteratively. By aligning with the cutting edge of innovation, Living Labs offer researchers a unique space to refine and fine-tune their work, ensuring that it remains at the forefront of advancements in the field. Through these invaluable resources, researchers can drive their projects towards real-world impact and contribute meaningfully to societal progress.

4.4.5 Customer segments in Health and Wellbeing Living Labs

End user: A person who ultimately uses or is intended to ultimately use the product, service or process. In living lab projects, the end user is defined as a primary study participant who voluntarily participates in research after giving informed consent to be the subject of the research.

Living lab research infrastructure end user: A person or organization who purchases or uses living lab research infrastructure services to conduct a specific contract-based research and development activity (often focusing on specifically defined end user group). Living lab research infrastructure end user can also be study participant (a.k.a. end user), if living project is focusing on developing living lab services and infrastructure.

End users can be classified as non-professional and professional groups. Typical non-professional and professional end-user groups in health and wellbeing includes the following:

- **Non-professional end users:**
 - **Consumers:** Those who buy goods or services for their own use.
 - **Public health and social service clients:** Those who use public services.
- **Professional end users**
 - **Health professionals and managers:** A person providing health care treatment and advice based on formal training and experience. Also known as healthcare professional or healthcare worker.
 - **Social care workers and managers:** Those providing the practical support to help people cope with the day-to-day business of living based on formal training and experience.
 - **Policy and decisions makers:** Those responsible for making policies and decisions at local, regional, national or international level.

Business-to-Business Customer (B2B): B2B-customer is an organization that purchases living lab services from a living lab. B2B-customers can be classified to private, public, education/research, civil society organizations and networks/cluster groups as follows:

- **Private sector organizations:** (business developers and researchers)
 - Tangible equipment and device manufactures
 - Health and social service providers
 - e-health, IT system and digital technology providers
 - Wellbeing and wellness service providers
 - Pharmaceutical companies
- **Public sector organizations:**

- **Local level:** Municipals, cities and other local level public organizations providing e.g., health and social services such as primary health care.
- **Regional level:** e.g., regional hospitals providing secondary and tertiary care, councils, parliaments, and governments as well as other administrative organizations operating at regional level.
- **National level:** Government agencies, departments or temporary pointed working groups responsible for the specific functions such as health and social services.
- **International level:** European commission departments and agencies as well as other organizations operating at international and transnational level.
- **Public funder:** Government or other European, national, regional or local public institutions who is providing public funding for a specific living lab living lab research project via call for application process.
- **Education and research organizations:**
 - **Higher education institutes:** Universities and Universities of Applied Sciences
 - **Other educational institutes** covering early childhood, primary, secondary and tertiary education.
 - **Public research institutions/organizations** such as technical research centers and government laboratories.
 - **Private research organizations** such as technology and innovation centers
- **Civil society organizations:**
 - Non-governmental organizations (NGO) and nonprofit entities operating at international, national, regional or local level.
- **Networks and clusters:**
 - Company cluster organizations and company networks
 - International, national, regional and local networks

Typical approaches to define non-professional end users (a.k.a. study participants) in health and wellbeing living lab projects are presented in Table 8.

Table 8 - Classification approaches of non-professional end users commonly acting as a primary study participant in a health and wellbeing living lab research project

Age groups			
Specific age range			
Adolescents	Adults	Older Adults	General Population
Adolescents Health status (disease, disorder or disability)			
Healthy			
Adults Health status (disease, disorder or disability)			
Healthy	Schizophrenia	Multiple-Sclerosis	Parkinson Disease
Post-Stroke Patients with Moving or Linguistic Disability	Mild Cognitive Impairment	Sleep Disorders: e.g., Apnea, Hypopnea	With Disability
Healthy with Possible Chronic Conditions			
Older Adults Health status (disease, disorder or disability)			
Healthy	Parkinson Disease	Mild Cognitive Impairment	With Disability
Healthy with Possible Chronic Conditions			

General Population Health status (disease, disorder or disability)			
Healthy	Ipf Patients	Prostate Cancer	Down Syndrome
Chronical Diseases: e.g., Persons With Chronic Pulmonary (Copd)	Cardiological Or Other Conditions (Aphasia)	Breast Cancer Survivors	

Typical approaches to define professional end users in health and wellbeing living lab projects are presented in Table 9.

Table 9 - Classification approaches of professional end users, students and organisations commonly acting as a primary study participant in a health and wellbeing living lab research project

Informal Caregivers			
Part of adults and citizens' group			
Health Care Professionals / Formal Caregivers			
Doctors	Social workers	Physiotherapists	Psychologists
Registered nurses	Practical nurses	Physicians	
Students			
Medical	Engineering	Computer Science	Pedagogues
English Literature	Nursing	Physiotherapy	Social Services.
Health Care Management			
Organizations			
Hospitals	Nursing homes	Care homes	Home care Organizations
Network organizations	Day care centers		

Living lab research infrastructure end users and B2B-customers in health and wellbeing living lab projects are presented in Table 10.

Table 10 - Researchers' expertise

Researchers' expertise	Brief use case description
Citizen scientists, users as co-researchers	User empowerment, training, design, analysis and implementation of strategies and methodologies for user engagement and for raising awareness and generating citizen participation.

Computer, technology scientists	Developing systems/tools/ technologies, testing and evaluating an ICT tool, prototype and real-life testing, computer vision & AI, Virtual Reality & Augmented Reality, Cybersecurity.
Data scientists	Collecting, analysing and interpreting digital data, such as data analytics in healthcare and digital patient recordings (how patient information recording process is managed and utilized during the intervention by using digital tools in simulated situations).
Rehabilitation (physical, cognitive) experts	Physiology, physiotherapy, occupational health research, rehabilitation and prevention. Cognitive diseases assistive technology, neuromuscular rehabilitation assistive technology.
UX research and assessment experts	Developing the process for user experience design (UXD, UED, or XD) supporting user behaviour through usability, usefulness, and desirability provided in the interaction with a product or service, addressing all aspects as perceived by users with a focus on the quality of the user experience. Studying and experimenting the best practices for UI/UX and evaluating user's experience in different situations and while using different tools.
Clinical researchers expertise	(Doctors, nurses, healthcare workers, specialists, physiotherapists etc.), conducting research of healthcare services and practices, research on symptomatology or epidemiology of a disease, analysis of clinical effects of research performed in the study, e.g., via real life testing.
Policymakers	Studying the impact of new service models or new collaboration models in healthcare, designing or improving policies, gathering requirements for improving health and wellbeing of citizens, co-creation of research methodologies for policy making.
Biomedical researchers	Studying biochemical and physiological functions, investigating how the human body works with the aim of finding new ways to improve health. Biomedical engineering knowledge (Home hospitalization, Transitional Care, Multifunctional interaction), as well as digital biomarkers analysis (e.g., for cognitive state).
Business developers	Studying the product-market fit, matching a solution with a societal need, learning about the user acceptance of products and services, as well as about potential products to develop, willingness to pay, business model and ideal route to market.
Innovation and design management researchers	Ecosystem and innovation management research, social network analysis. Evaluating how health and wellbeing ecosystem operates between different actors at local, regional, national and international level, including also scaling and commercialization.
Accessibility design experts	Validating accessible architectonics and escape route models with VR experiment and real-life simulations.
Ergonomics and safety experts	Implementation and validation of ergonomic technologies/services to support workers and system performance, promoting ergonomics in

	working environments, improving both health/well-being and productivity, while avoiding occupational hazards.
Organizational studies experts	Co-creation, experimentation, organizational research, experts by experience / peer support included. Evaluation how multistakeholder collaboration and co-creation is done and how effective it is. Evaluates experimentations and experimentation culture. How users are involved into these processes.
Neuroscientists	Focusing on the brain and its impact on behaviour and cognitive functions (cognitive neuroscience, EEG-based BMI research, protocol / paradigm testing, study framework evaluation).
Psychologists (clinical, social, developmental, neuro)	Studying the behaviour and the mental wellbeing of participants, conducting psychometrics evaluation and real-life setting experimentation/observation/real life testing.
Social workers/researchers	Conducting an investigation in accordance with the scientific methods and tools, studying the impact of new care models and/or care innovations on society, developing models for a caring and inclusive society.
Sport science experts	Experimenting novel training methods, and their effectiveness in various dimensions such as safety, engagement, and physical capabilities. Studying the impact of physical movements in various functions and wellbeing features.
Communication studies experts	Defining written, oral, visual and digital communication within a certain workplace. Evaluating (multi professional) healthcare team collaboration, communication and debriefing in various healthcare situations in simulated environments (especially in Simulation lab).
Performing arts experts	Creative health improvement (e.g., for cognitive decline) through music and dance (example: redesigning public spaces into healthy spaces: test and validate Smart methodologies, products and services through folk dance).
Pedagogues/educators	Evaluating different pedagogical approaches and their impact learning performance (especially in Simulation lab).
Applied economics experts	Evaluating cost and performance in different healthcare processes, situations and public health.

4.4.6 Channels

Living lab channels includes following:

Table 11 - Living Lab Channels

Projects	Participating as a partner or coordinator in projects including all project activities.
Physical and digital development and testing environments	All real-life (e.g. hospital, outdoors, office, home), laboratory (e.g. simulation lab) and virtual (e.g. game) environments where testing and co-creation is done.

Direct channels	Direct one-to-one and one-to-many marketing, personal contact network, email, telco, word of mouth)
Event and conference participation and arrangement	Participating in events, fairs, scientific and professional conferences either as a participant or presenter. Hosting and arranging conferences and events, periodical events for living lab innovation ecosystem stakeholders.
Scientific and professional publications	Publications written by Living Lab personnel to describe Living Lab activities and results to professional and scientific audiences.
Online, mobile and social media or collaboration platforms.	Web and mobile sites, social media services, youtube and other similar digital media services and collaboration platforms. The Accelup collaboration platform (https://accelup.eu/home) serves as a meeting place for innovators and accredited living labs. Innovators can post a project, receive bids from living labs, select a living lab to conduct the project, pay for the service, and finally rate the service.
Training courses and education	Degree programs and training courses focusing on living lab topics, Internship as a part of studies
Paid media promotion and marketing	Media campaigns, printed media, PR-activities
Official public sector channels	Official channel managed by local, regional, national or international public authorities such as funded project databases (e.g. CORDIS). The information regarding living lab research infrastructure on PaneLab (https://app.thepanelab.com/) are publicly available through the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).
Partner channels	Communication in collaboration with living lab partner network. See more details in partners section.
Lobbying and policy channels	Public sector policy and strategy papers and recommendations, advisory meetings, Information meetings with hospitals and administrative

4.4.7 Customer relationships

Living lab customer relationship includes following customer relationships

Table 12 - Living Lab customer relationships

Long-term partnership relations	Partnerships and contacts grounded to promote living labs beyond single project e.g. with local authorities, device manufacturers or research sites.
Project consortium and partnerships collaboration	Project based collaboration relationships based a defined project plan, typically in public funded projects.
Tailored project, consultation and advisory services via market access	Tailoring living lab projects and solutions to meet specific customer needs.
User communities and stakeholder engagement and orchestration	Engaging with end-users and user communities and other innovation ecosystem stakeholder via workshops, citizen science projects, co-design sessions, and other forms of participatory engagement.
Direct personal contacts	email, phone, face-to-face, skype

Academic partnerships	Joint research activities via research projects, student involvement, knowledge exchange activities, and access to academic expertise and resources.
Industry collaboration	Industry partners providing funding, expertise, or access to facilities, while living labs offer a platform for testing and validating new products, services, or processes in real-world settings.
Government engagement	Collaboration relationships with local, regional, national and international level to address sustainability challenges, inform policy decisions, and facilitate the adoption of innovative solutions. Government engagement may include co-funding initiatives, regulatory support, access to infrastructure, and participation in pilot projects or demonstration programs.
Startup Entrepreneurial Ecosystems and	Supporting startups, entrepreneurs, and innovation hubs to develop and commercialize of new ideas and technologies.
Collaboration with other living labs	Collaboration with other local, regional, national or international living labs to share best practices, exchange knowledge, and collaborate on cross-cutting research or innovation projects.
Funding sponsorship and	Relationships with funding organizations, philanthropic foundations, corporate sponsors, or venture capitalists to secure financial support for living lab. Also providing funding to SMEs and researcher via open calls.
Hosting organization internal relationships	Collaboration with hosting organization additional human resources and access to infrastructure.

4.4.8 Cost Structure

Living lab cost categories includes following:

Table 13 - Living lab cost categories

Personnel	All personnel related expenditure including salaries, human resource management, administrative costs, and internship fees. Since personnel are generating the majority of living labs costs, the living lab service list presented in Table X can be used for evaluating and estimating the operational costs related to personnel. Adding living lab personnel roles such as living lab manager, researcher, or facilitator as columns will provide an even more focused understanding of cost distribution.
Infrastructure facilities cost and	All facilities, technical environments (rent and investment), equipment, amortisation and depreciation of equipment, (software) licences, utilities costs, common costs, memberships fees and financial costs (interest rate). Classification of living lab data collection devices can also act as a tool to keep track of technology-related costs such as license fees or purchase costs.
R&D development	Software, process, concept, or other similar tools development which are required to run or improve Living Lab activities, own share of external funded projects
Travelling costs	Domestics and international travelling costs
IPR protection fees	Patents and IPR protection

End-user fees and other variable costs relating project activities	Arranging living lab activities (e.g. facility rent, food, transportation, insurance), payments for end-user participation, materials and consumables.
Outsourced services and subcontracting costs	ICT infrastructure outsource expenditure (e.g. hosting costs), all other professional service costs e.g. for dissemination purposes (print, graphical design), legal guidance, external experts such as medical doctors.
Marketing, sales and dissemination	Marketing, communication, customer and end-user acquisition costs, engaging users, conference and event participations.

4.4.9 Revenue Streams

Living lab revenue streams includes following

Table 14 - Living Lab revenue streams

Public funded project grants	Grants received from local, regional, national and international funding calls such Horizon, Interreg, European Social Fund (ESF). European Regional Development Fund (EARF).
Fixed funding and annual collaboration contracts/Agreements	Basic funding beyond single project from 1) living owners or hosting organization, 2) local, regional or national authorities.
Market driven access fees	1) Contracts and invoicing from executing R&D projects (testing and co-creation), 2) consulting and advisory services, 3) recruiting test groups for customers, 4) event participation fees
Training courses and education fees	1) Training course fees, 2) examination fees, 3) certification fees and 4) site visits to living lab.
Device and infrastructure rental fees	Rental living lab equipment and facilities
In-kind sponsorship	Free of charge equipment provided by technology providers to be used or offered to customers in a dedicated space or for project purposes.
Donations	Individual or institutional donators
Royalties	Royalties from IP properties or elsewhere
Crowdfunding	Reward based crowdfunding (donors can earn rewards based on the amount of money they donate).

4.4.10 Living Lab Key Performance Indicators

Here we present the current version of the Living Lab Key Performance Indicators, derived by the activities described in section 2.6.

Table 15 - Living Lab Key Performance Indicators

Chapter	Criterion	KPI
Strategy	Governance	1. % of involvement of different stakeholders in the vision/mission (e.g., all Q4/5 represented is 100%)
		2. % of involvement of different stakeholders in the governance, supported by the necessary partner agreements (including clear actor roles)
		3. Presence of SMART goals and decision-making processes (responsibilities)

	Business Model	4. Presence of a business model (canvas), including customers, value proposition, resources, revenues, and costs (e.g., LIAISON)
		5. Presence of a service portfolio covering (all) phases of the lifecycle approach
		6. Presence of partner agreements/arrangement for co-innovation
	Culture Collaboration &	7. % Who's paying/contributing with what (private & public funding, revenues service portfolio)
		8. Internal & external relation management process/strategy in place (including client contracts)
		9. Frequency of internal communication & results sharing
Operations	Human Resources	10. Number of regional, national & international (long-term) collaborations
		11. Implementation of clear internal roles and responsibilities
		12. Amount of qualified (internal/external) staff (Full-Time-Equivalent)
	Operations	13. % of Role flexibility within the organization (i.e., how many (different/multiple) people can execute (different/multiple) roles)
		14. Number of (finished) living lab projects and/or activities/ 3 year
		15. Quality of internal monitoring framework (strategic, financial, equipment & infrastructure, policy, project outcomes)
	Equipment infrastructure &	16. Frequency of monitoring the living lab and its main activities
		17. Presence of facilities
		18. Presence of hard- and software
	Openness	Innovation partnerships, projects & processes
20. Level of reflective & iterative approach to transdisciplinary collaboration		
21. Transparency of project roles, selection & execution (including accessible and understandable information)		
		22. Presence of an ethical approach (e.g., regulatory requirements, data protection needed)

	Ownership of results	23. Presence of strategy & processes for ownership of the rights & profits (including data) of collaborative outcomes
		24. Presence of rules & regulations regarding the use, sharing & licensing of intellectual property (prior to the project)
		25. Presence of user agreements (data, intellectual property, rights, liabilities)
Users reality &	User centrality	26. Diversity of profiled end users
		27. (% of the) Role of end users according to the levels of involvement
		28. Level of permanence of the user panel beyond living lab projects
	Lifecycle & real-life	29. Number of users involved in the different phases of the innovation cycle
		30. Concreteness of real-life settings enabling users to participate in their natural environments
		31. % of time of user involvement within real-life settings
	Tools & methods	32. Proof of a structured & transparent approach/strategy for active user involvement throughout the innovation cycle
		33. Range tools & methods for the different phases of the innovation cycle
		34. Proof of a transparent (concept, background, process, outcomes & results) communication approach/strategy tailored to the different types of stakeholders
Impact value &	Co-created values	35. % Satisfaction of users/stakeholders (from the whole value chain) concerning their involvement/influence
		36. Frequency of knowledge sharing (including results) with relevant (internal & external) stakeholders from the value chain
		37. Number of (open) educational resources (including datasets) shared/provided for relevant stakeholders
		38. % Satisfaction of users/stakeholders concerning knowledge sharing & capacity building (learning materials & infrastructures)
	Impacts	39. Presence of an impact assessment framework & procedures
		40. Frequency of impact assessments

		41. % of improvement of organizational excellence (e.g., working procedures/processes, desired knowledge & skills)
Stability & harmonization	Stability	42. % Increase of relationships with a reliable partner network and customers
		43. Level of financial maturity based on a balanced & diversified set of funding & revenue streams
		44. Number of living lab value propositions, flexible to adapt to eventual new needs
	Harmonization scale-up &	45. % Increase of partners committed to scale up products/solutions/services
		46. Number of products/solutions/services (able to be) scaled-up
		47. % increase of influence on and/or collaboration with other (networks of) living labs
		48. Number of transferred living lab infrastructures, standards, skills, methods, tools, processes & services to other (networks) of living labs and/or relevant actors
		49. Number of adopted harmonized living lab infrastructures, standards, skills, methods, tools, processes & services
		50. Number of (cross-border/cross-sectoral) initiatives/projects based on common processes

4.4.11 Research and Innovation process

This tool offers a graphical depiction of the Living Lab Research and Innovation process, catering to external researchers and research teams interested in conducting research within a Living Lab environment. Its purpose is to assist them in identifying the necessary steps to undertake. Once the initial Touchpoints (highlighted in the blue column) have been identified, researchers can then follow the process guidelines while maintaining open and effective communication with the respective Living Lab throughout their research activities.

Figure 9 - Current version of the Living Lab Research and Innovation process map

Color coding: In the illustration the following color coding is used: White boxes are referring to R&D-services where the living lab is in direct contact with its’ customers. Grey color boxes indicate that the service is back-office services having more administrative and R&D support function. Auxiliary services indicated with hexagon are auxiliary processes interlink with living lab activities.

4.5 PART 3. Research process

Table 16 below presents the Living Lab research process phases and details about the services that Living Labs can offer in each phase. These phases are inspired by research in the Health and Wellbeing domain but can be extended to other domains as well.

Table 16 - Living Lab Research Phases

Phases	Research process steps	Related living lab services
Planning phase	1. Identifying the research problem	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use living lab capacity building services to gain knowledge and skills to conduct your own living lab study. Conduct small pre-study with a living lab. Use e.g., co-creation sessions or expert opinion services to gain better understanding of the research topic or to formulate robust research design. Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping with living lab to determine suitable sample. Use open data repository and omit data collection entirely or partially.
	2. Conduct literature review and collect other relevant background information	
	3. Formulate research questions and/or hypothesis	
	4. Define the research design and determine sample	
	Acquire funding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Apply temporary living lab research funding if it is available e.g., via open call.

Preparation phase		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Utilize living lab grant writing and funding application support services or join to consortium who is applying funding. Use living lab networking services to gain access with funders.
	Research infrastructure selection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Get in contact with a living lab and familiarize yourself with their research infrastructure key assets and service offerings. Living lab research infrastructure covers single-sited, distributed, virtual access and mobility facilities, which each have different strengths. Clarify your research needs in intake and matching process with potential living lab infrastructure providers. Wait for their offer. Send equipment and/or facility rental request to a living lab.
	Ethic approval	Living lab will prepare and manage ethical application process for your study.
	Participant recruitment	Living lab will use their stakeholder population repository to recruit study participants for the study.
Implementation phase	5. Data collection	Living lab will conduct data collection according to research protocol and will manage the project for you. You will benefit from wide range available methods, tools, devices, technologies, validated questionnaires and instruments, which can be tailored to your research needs.
	6. Analyze data	Living lab will conduct data analysis if agreed in project contract. Translations or summary reports from local language to English are made if there isn't common language between customer and collected data.
	7. Interpret results	Discuss and interpret result in a co-creative manner with diverse group of experts from living lab innovation ecosystem.
	8. Write research report	Co-author scientific and professional publications with living lab researchers.
Dissemination and valorisation	9. Disseminate findings	Utilize living lab sales, marketing and networking services to disseminate and valorise your research results to various stakeholder groups. Gain visibility by sharing your publication in living lab publication repository.

4.6 PART 4. Innovation process

Table 17 presents the Living Lab innovation process phases with detailed information about the activities performed at each stage. The Living Lab Innovation process stems from the TRL levels of innovation process.

Table 17 - Living Lab innovation process Phases

Title	Research environment	Solution name	Functionality, Interactivity	Solution maturity	Exploratory research aim	Confirmatory research aim
TRL 1: Need assessment and ideation	Laboratory	Idea	None	A group of needs, problems, opportunities and/or ideas identified. Not been proven feasible.	Investigate a problem or topic to generate new ideas and hypotheses.	Prioritize needs and ideas.
TRL 2: Concept co-creation	Laboratory	Visual prototype	None, or very limited	High-level speculative and static concept transforming to concept prototype without or very limited functionality. Focuses on explaining and describing overall design concept and user interactions. Based on sketches, diagrams, drawings, compositions, mock-ups, wireframes, digital models, storyboards, paper interface and/or descriptive text. Non interactive to very	Investigate a topic in more detailed to co-create and formulate concept and value hypotheses in iterative or parallel manner.	Prioritize options to determine the most appropriate way to proceed with further development.
TRL 3: Proof-of-concept (POC)	Laboratory	Alpha prototype	Very limited		Explore different human, technical, economic, and environmental aspects to verify what is the best approach to develop the solution.	Test value hypothesis and confirm or reject them. Focus on user acceptance and feasibility.

				limited interactivity		
TRL 4: Prototyping in lab	Laboratory		Limited	User experience / working prototypes transforming from low to moderate depth and breadth of functionality. First working models to identify and	Co-create rapid functional prototype versions. Focus on the basic functionalities.	Verify usability, and technical feasibility to find out the most promising options having highest cost/profit ratio and user acceptance.
TRL 5: Prototyping in relevant environment	Relevant		Moderate	resolve usability, design and technical issues. Can have substantial flaws or missing functions.	Continue to iteratively refine the prototype based on the collected feedback and co-creation inputs.	Validate that prototype as a whole and at component / subsystem level is working and performs as expected while meeting the predictions.
TRL 6: Demonstration in relevant environment	Relevant	Beta prototype	High or near full	High-fidelity prototype with near fully functionality that closely resemble the final solution and adequately addresses all critical features. Technical feasibility fully demonstrated.		Validate that prototype as a whole can operate reliable and consistently over time and is ready for operational usage.

TRL 7: Small scale demonstration in operational environment	Operational		Near full or full	Production prototype near final solution (or final solution) functioning at system level		By using rigorous evidence-based data validate social/human, economic viability, scalability, positive/negative effects, as well as any unintended consequences or indirect impacts that may arise in operational environment. Start in small scale and increase the scale gradually to full scale.
TRL 8: Full scale demonstration in operational environment	Operational	Pilot prototype	Full	Final complete solution at system level.	Refine and commit to final solution.	
TRL 9: Post market testing / surveillance	Operational	Final solution	Full	Final complete solution at system level ready for sale.	Refinement via versioning strategy.	Monitor and evaluate safety, effectiveness, performance and quality over longer period of time.

4.7 PART 5. R&D Services

R&D services refer to a group of common R&D services, which a Living Lab can offer to its customers during the different Living Lab R&D process phases. Each service combines one or more data collection approaches or other activities. R&D Services are parts of the Living Lab standard needed to accomplish a Living Lab R&D project as a whole or part of it. Each service description defines the type of service and additional details related to service delivery such as technical and functional quality. Living lab R&D services are classified into the following categories:

1. Testing and validation
2. Community and network building
3. Project planning and management
4. Co-creation
5. Capacity building
6. Advisory services
7. Market and sales support
8. Infrastructure and data management

It is noted that some of the services can be included in multiple categories.

Table 18 - Living Lab Services Categorization

SERVICE NAME	Service type			Process phase		
	R&D	Back-office	Auxiliary	Customer acquisition	Detailed project planning	Project implementation and dissemination
Access to data	X			X		
Application evaluation		X		X		
Capacity building	X			X		
Contract / Consortium agreement		X		X		
Desk / Market research (for project planning purposes)		X		X	X	
Equipment and facility rental service				X		
Funding application process			X	X		
Funding call information			X	X		
Funding call monitoring		X		X		
Grant writing / Preparation				X		
Innovation network orchestration				X	X	X
Intake and matching	X			X		
Maintenance		X		X		
Marketing, sales and networking support				X		
Offer preparation		X		X		
Stakeholder analysis				X	X	X
Subcontracting negotiation process		X		X		
Temporary research funding		X		X		
(Data) Access management		X			X	
Data governance policy		X			X	
Data management plan		X			X	
Detailed project planning		X			X	
Ethical application preparation		X			X	
Ethics committee review			X		X	
IPR management		X			X	X
Research protocol design		X			X	
Research site permit			X		X	
Resource allocation		X			X	
Clinical trials	X					X
Co-creation sessions	X					X

Competitor and market analysis and benchmarking	x					x
Concept and proof-of-concept tests – feasibility study	x					x
Data analysis		x				x
Data anonymization and pseudonymization		x				x
Data cleaning		x				x
Dissemination		x				x
Expert opinion and advisory services						x
Fair data compliance process		x				x
Foresighting (trends, weak signals and wild cards)	x					x
Idea selection and testing	x					x
Impact assessment and validation test	x					x
Large-scale real-life testing and piloting	x					x
Legal, regulation and safety standard support	x					x
Living lab project management		x				x
Panel management		x				x
Post-market surveillance and market acceptance testing	x					x
Prototyping test	x					x
Public procurement support services	x					x
Quality and risk management		x				x
Results reporting / Publication writing		x				x
Simulation test	x					x
Small-scale real-life testing and experimentation	x					x
Stakeholder engagement		x				x
Usability testing	x					x

Depending on the nature and the scope of each service, the structure and the elements of the descriptive information vary. Below, follows a brief explanation of the R&D services structure:

Table 19 - R&D Services Structure

Section	Description
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Description	In the description field a general overview of the service is given (e.g., definition, scope, followed processes etc.)
R&D service categories	Here it is indicated the category (or categories) to which belongs the service
Key characteristics in living lab context	In this field are highlighted the most important points/aspects of the service in a Living Lab framework
Pre-tasks	By pre-tasks we mean the several steps that are considered important to be completed before the delivery of the service
Participants' role	Participants' role refers to the particular actions/activities that are expected to be achieved by the stakeholders during the service delivery
Objectives	In this part are identified the various goals that are envisaged to be accomplished during the delivery of the service
Methods	This field refers to the methodology that stakeholders could follow for the service implementation (e.g., focus groups, training sessions, workshops, seminars, presentations, interviews etc.)
Tools	By tools we mean the specific instruments which could be possibly exploited during the service (e.g., questionnaires, sensors, Teams meeting, Zoom, whiteboards etc.)
Process phase	Here it is indicated the phase or stage during which the service is usually delivered

4.7.1 Expert opinion, and advisory services

Description: Expert(s) who have long-standing practical and/or scientific experience in the field of enquiry provide(s) a well-founded written or oral answer for your questions, including the ethics domain/ethics guidelines, and offer(s) advisory services on the use of specific equipment. Expert(s) are discussing ideas and problems from a different angle to respectfully challenge, test and refine ideas (e.g., as devil's advocate looking for problems). Qualified and traceable arguments in favor of and against a specific position in an applied issue to support decision-making and development activities. Professional work is a paid service, but "consultation" can be a free of charge service. In most cases it is done by Living Lab on its own, or hosting organization personnel.

R&D service category-ies: Project planning and management, Capacity building, Advisory services, Market and sales support

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Typically consists of one-to-one relationship between the customer and the expert but may include opinions from multiple experts.
- Internal or external experts (local, national and international experts)
- Multidisciplinary collaboration/Pool of experts

Objectives:

- Offer advice on UX or usability studies,
- Consulting care solutions (ICT and devices), in specific/narrow fields in which Living Lab has experts (e.g., energy consumption calculations),
- Consulting on consent and ethics requirement and processes,
- Consulting technical solutions (ICT, medical and other devices, sensors, wearables, health apps, machine learning, medical engineering)
- Consulting legal issues, networking and contacting people (e.g., doctors, academia, pharmacy, healthcare professionals, policy makers, local ecosystem actors), research ideas,
- Innovation management, interventions,
- Creation of training materials and processes

Methods: One to one and group discussion, advisory board, expert identification

Tools/Online tools: ethical tools, training materials

4.7.2 Idea selection and testing

Description: Idea testing is a low-cost and quick process in which high-level ideas are selected (i.e., ranked) or tested with real end-users via different methods such as interviews, surveys or during the workshop. In order to conduct idea testing, different high-level ideas are pre-described in written or in visual format, and then communicated to the real end-users or experts. The main aim is to collect feedback on the already existing idea proposal. Feedback can also include improvement suggestions.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation, Co-creation

Objectives:

- Collect feedback, prioritize ideas or different alternative options,
- Lowering development risk by selecting the best/most promising idea for further development,
- Challenge the ideas from different perspectives

Methods: Co-creation workshop, interviews, focus groups, surveys, questionnaires, small group discussions, informal talks

4.7.3 Co-creation session

Description: Co-creation session is a facilitated group activity to find solutions for a specific problem by gathering ideas, solutions and insights from workshop participants while using variety of methods. Depending on the workshop focus, it may comprise ideation, concept development and testing. Typical duration for short workshop is from 45 minutes to 90 minutes, medium-length workshop from 90 minutes to 3 hours, and long-workshop from 3 hours to 1 day. The number of participants may vary depending on how many facilitators are available, and what kind of working methods are utilized. Typically, a workshop facilitated by a single facilitator consists of six to eight persons. Number of participants are sometimes numbered to enable them to work in pairs.

R&D service category-ies: Co-creation, Capacity building

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Fundamental features: Requires (1) facilitator(s), (2) interaction/is interactive, (3) iterative process
- Can be applied in almost all phases: e.g., ideation, concept creation/testing, prototyping, prototype testing
- Can be virtual/online or in person event
- It is a service but also a generic method
- Duration varies, but usually 2-3 hours

- Often multi-stakeholder approach: researchers, clinicians, students (e.g., paediatric project, project on language and communication). Depending on the concept all actors of the quadruple helix are contacted, number of users depends also on the stakeholders. Engagement of different stakeholders can also be achieved by running series of sessions

Participants' role:

- In the beginning of the innovation process, involve the users as the creators
- If there is a product with higher Technology Readiness Level (TRL), a ready Minimum Viable Product (MVP) is more like a focus group,
- Need finding session, focus group is more of an evaluation,

Pre-tasks: prepare session upfront with the sketches, if focus group - open questions (sent beforehand), workshop preparation template

Objectives (varies depending on researchers' interest):

- Co-creation session: Finding solutions for a specific problem with or without prototypes or mock-ups. Co-creating the actual design, sketch interfaces, make the solution tangible, Drafting (prototypes, drawing), mock-ups
- Demo-session: specifically, setup to explain about the use of a prototype or market ready product and gather (first) feedback. Often done before launching a test.
- Business model session (broader, a service?): developing and defining a business model (e.g., potential customers, sales channels, distributors, value chain, the Willingness to Pay, revenue streams etc.

Methods: Brainstorming, use simulations, group discussion / focus groups, semi-structured focus group, survey, questionnaire

Tools: Projection walls, visual mock-ups, use tangible tools for prototyping (e.g., wearables), team groups, polling (tech); questionnaires, focus groups, idea generation techniques, post-it notes, creative supplies, art supplies,

Online tools: Online system for idea generation, Teams meeting, Zoom with breakout rooms, Google meet, Miro whiteboard, Mural.co

4.7.4 Impact assessment and validation test

Description: Impact assessment is a formal, evidence-based procedure that assesses the total outcome that comes as a result of the tested activity, above and beyond what would have happened anyway. Depending on the duration and scope of the validation process impact can be evaluated on individuals, organizations and the society in the short, medium and long term. Validation is the documented act of demonstration that a product or a service will consistently lead to the expected results. Validation test ensures that the product or the service actually meets the defined requirements and demonstrates that the solution fulfils its intended use when deployed on appropriate real environment.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- The validation test is usually designed by LL
- Validation testing has to meet some minimum TRL level in order reliable test the solution impact

Objectives:

- Verify that the developed solution will consistently lead to the expected results and meet defined requirement
- Evaluate social impact
- Quantify change after solution usage

Methods: Survey, observation, pre and post measurement (short and long term), quantitative measures (e.g., physiological measures), feasibility study, usability study, interviews

Tools/online tools: Questionnaires, validated scientific scale/questionnaires, sensors, thermal cameras

4.7.5 Concept and proof-of-concept tests – concept feasibility study

Description: Concept test is a low cost and quick process in which a high-level concept is tested with real end-users via different methods such as interviews and surveys. In order to conduct a concept test, preliminary concept description must exist in written or visual format, which is then communicated to the real end-users or experts. The main aim is to collect feedback for the initial concept proposal and its possible variations. Concept test can also include a feasibility study, which also covers technical, economic, legal, operational and scheduling issues relating the proposed concept. In all, concept-testing phase verifies if a concept has market interest, while feasibility study shows if the product or service based on concept can be developed. Collected feedback also includes improvement suggestions.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation, Co-creation

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Core service in LL

Participants' role: Two main actors (projects and companies), joint work among Living Labs and interested partners/stakeholders

Process phase: After concept co-creation

Objectives:

- Verify if a concept has market or research interest,
- Testing early “prototypes” to get feedback for development, identify improvement suggestions,
- Concept feasibility test focuses on verifying if concept can be technically/economically done (preliminary assessment),
- Provide development recommendations based on user/patient/customer experience and needs, identify key measures to investigate in follow-up tests, personalized in the client need and varies case by case

Methods: Survey, demo-session, interview, Wizard of Oz

Tools: Paper prototype, visual dummies close to final (visual UI), visual VR can be used to test-multitasking (real work), long term evaluations, interviews, questionnaires

4.7.6 Innovation network orchestration

Description: Establishing productive working relationship between existing and previously unconnected but complementary actor parties and helping them (companies, public health and other sector, academia, and end-user stakeholders) to work together properly and well. Handling conflicts and supporting interactions.

R&D service category-ies: Community and network building, Capacity building

Objectives:

- Establish new collaboration relationships,
- Promote Living Lab methodology and raising awareness,
- Lobbying Living Lab movement

Methods: Events, seminars, webinars, conferences, one-to-one meetings, site visits, publications (scientific and professional), memberships in local/regional/national/international associations/networks

4.7.7 Large-scale real-life testing and piloting

Description: Similar to small-scale testing but with a longer duration or larger number of test participants who are representing the real end-users of the target group. During piloting, the aim is to evaluate the full scale and near or fully functional product(s) or service(s) at the system level in real environment with real end-users to make sure that the solution is scalable. Includes often impact assessment and validation testing.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Usually, the aim of the testing defines the number of participants
- Sometimes, for large numbers the LL can hire a specialized company for support

Objectives:

- Evaluate scalability,
- Evaluate system level impact and functionality,

Methods: Testing in real-life setting with real users, longitudinal study, sensors, interview, survey, observation, ethnographic studies, diaries, qualitative/quantitative methods, pre and post measurement

4.7.8 Prototyping test

Description: Prototyping test is a low cost and quick process in which a product or service with limited functionality and interaction is tested with real end-users. An interactive prototype product or service must be available so real end-users or experts can experience it. This prototype test can be, for instance, an interactive mock-up of a web service, which interface looks like a real thing. One can navigate through different screens and see simulated content. Also, the service prototype can consist of role-playing exercise to simulate service encounters. The main aim is to collect feedback on a 'close to real' user experience as possible, but at a lower cost. Different methods such as interviews, surveys and observations can be used.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- From rapid prototyping to the MVP
- IT solutions/Physical and cognitive exercises

Objectives:

- Similar to proof-of-concept but testing higher fidelity solution,
- Identify improvement suggestions and usability test,
- Provides development recommendations based on user/patient/customer experience and needs,
- Identify key measures to investigate in follow-up tests

Methods: Survey, observation, demo-session, interview, Wizard of Oz, usability tests, role playing

Tools: Paper prototype, wireframes, interactive mock-ups, scaled down prototypes, visual dummies close to final (visual UI), video recording, usability questionnaires, eye tracking

4.7.9 Small-scale real-life testing and experimentation

Description: A small-scale real-life experiment is a small-scale and short-term preliminary study conducted to evaluate feasibility of the suggested product or service and to improve it based on the testing result. Testing includes a small number of test participants who are representing the real end-users of the target group.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation

Key characteristics in Living Lab context

- Usually lab-based studies
- Can mostly involve qualitative feedback
- Testing quality and user satisfaction,

Objectives:

- Verify that the developed solution will work also in real-life setting,
- Evaluate usability before engaging more people in testing,

Methods: Testing in real-life setting with real users, survey, interview, survey, observation, diaries, qualitative/quantitative methods, pre and post measurement

Tools: Validated questionnaires, sensors

4.7.10 Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping

Description: Identifying groups, organizations, and people who are relevant stakeholders. Prioritizing and ranking stakeholders based on their perspectives and interest. Mapping the relationship between different stakeholders and company objectives. Deliverable(s) written report.

R&D service category-ies: Community and network building, Project planning and management, Co-creation

Key characteristics in Living Lab context

- Within a research context / for programs and projects.
- Trying to promote a diversity-centered design

Pre-tasks: Searching and listing all the interested stakeholders/partners, contacting them, and then mapping possible contributors

Objectives:

- Identifying relevant/key/negative stakeholders,
- Identify stakeholders' interest,
- Provide information to participant recruitment

Methods: Focus group, workshop, interviews, questionnaires methodology, social network analysis, two-dimensional matrix (e.g., power, influence, interest/need, support/attitude), primary/secondary/tertiary stakeholder, the salience model

Tools: Online whiteboard (e.g., Miro), stakeholder mapping template

4.7.11 Usability testing

Description: Usability testing is a technique used to evaluate a product by testing it in order to give direct input on how real users use or would use the product or service. Usability inspection is conducted when a professional evaluator inspects a user interface and gives an expert opinion regarding the usability. This approach does not involve real user. Usability testing with real users includes real users who have no prior exposure to the product or service. In the context of Living Labs is mostly provided real user testing.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation

Objectives: Identify usability problems, provides development recommendations based on user/patient/customer experience and needs,

Methods: Moderated/unmoderated, remote/in-person, comparative testing, open ended explorative testing, user satisfaction, phone/video interview, usability lab testing, session recordings, observation

Tools: SUS, QUEST, feasibility assessment and other several tests, eye-tracking camera

4.7.12 Capacity building

Description: Training, knowledge sharing and awareness raising, site visits and event arrangement. Offering training for end-users and/or practitioners to improve their skills and knowledge about Living Lab approach, co-creation, iterative development and healthcare and wellbeing market. Stimulating knowledge sharing and awareness raising by publishing professional and scientific publications and arranging events, site visits and seminars.

R&D service category-ies: Capacity building

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- The way of knowledge sharing and transfer depends on the project and on the purpose
- Use of short-term or long-term methods and courses
- Material can be both created for a purpose but also some available online

Participants' role:

- Service beneficiaries become trainees
- Living Labs can offer support for the design and facilitation of capacity building programs

Methods: Co-creation methodology, focus groups, training sessions (tech & non-tech), ethical training & legal in large scale settings, seminars, presentations, workshops, webinars, forums, websites and web-engines, events, site visits, publications, summer schools, degree program, methodological training, how to use new product

4.7.13 Living Lab project planning and management

Description: Planning project goals, costs, schedule, list of deliverables, delivery dates and resources. Written project plan for one or multiple innovation stages is made. In the project management, planned tasks are completed by executing, monitoring, controlling, and closing the work of a project team to achieve specific goals and to meet specific success criteria at the specified time.

R&D service category-ies: Project planning and management

Objectives:

- Successful development and implementation of all project procedures,
- Supervision and quality control,
- Internal/external communication,
- Optimization of the allocated resources,
- Getting clients and funding,

Tools/Online tools: Project and planning management tools, Microsoft Teams, Microsoft Excel, email, phone, messaging application

4.7.14 Competitor and market analysis and benchmarking

Description: Quantitative and qualitative methods are used to evaluate the size of the market both, in volume and in value (also known as market studies). Customer segments, buying patterns, competition, and the economic environment are defined to identify the regulations and the barriers to entry. Defining the market by listing and describing current, future, direct and indirect competitors and analysing their competitive offering (e.g., SWOT) and user experience. Comparing offerings by measuring the performance of the developed products, services, or processes against those, which are considered to be the best in the industry. Can consist also of literature reviews to a search and evaluation of the available scientific or professional body of knowledge for the given subject or chosen topic area.

R&D service category-ies: Advisory services, Market and sales support

Participants' role: Competitors or stakeholders interested in collaborations, can be done by students or experts.

Objectives:

- Identify the “space” for innovation, not analysing only specific segments, but also looking for new opportunities
- Analyse market acceptance, support scalability and transferability potential, focus can be domestic/international/global market,
- Identify direct and/or indirect competitors, qualitative or quantitative description of the market, focus can also be in research context or innovation management practices

Methods: Desk research, acquiring the information from the experts in the field, following the market as a job profile/duty, the people working know specific segments/areas, bibliometric studies, literature reviews to a search and evaluate of the available scientific or professional body of knowledge for the given subject or chosen topic area, technology exploitation, market analysis, benchmarking, other methods combined with interview(s) with a leading reference organisation or expert(s), assessment of technologies, knowledge syntheses (systematic and scoping reviews), evaluations methods of intervention (ETMI method), workshops and sessions, measures of satisfaction of users

Tools: SWOT analysis, business model canvas, Innovation management standard (CEN/TS 16555 - covered 7 standards, after ISO 56002:2019)

4.7.15 Intake and matching

Description: During this service, the customer's (e.g., a company, SME, a start-up, a researcher) development and testing needs are clarified for the project planning purposes. It also includes the process of mapping the customer's needs and co-designing of the strategic planning in relation to the target/purpose of the project and Living Lab capabilities to offer the particular project.

R&D service category-ies: Community & Network building, Co-creation, Advisory services

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Can be both open discussion or more focused
- Usually at the beginning of the research process
- Can be virtual/online or in person event
- Duration varies-30 minutes (very short from) to few hours or days. In most of the cases there are multiple meetings taking place/more than one contact
- Often multi-stakeholder approach: Researchers, clinicians, customers, students

Participants' role:

- Customers as co-creators

Pre-tasks:

- Discuss and understand who the customers are and what their needs are.
- Agree to a plan -usually it is made a document/contract- (set goals, explore the different services, engage the operational team
- Revise & follow-up activities with the customer

Objectives

- Make a project proposal/offer between the relevant stakeholders
- Make a project contract

Methods:

Client's needs elicitation methodology, interview/focus group/questionnaires for defining the project and collecting the needs, co-design of the strategic planning in relation to the target/purpose of the project

4.7.16 Simulation test

Description: Simulation is a technique that creates a situation and environment, which allows end-users to experience a representation of a real event in a risk-free environment. A predefined simulation scenario defines a particular set of conditions to resemble authentic situations in a location where a simulation experience takes place to test and to gain understanding of tested solution and related human interactions. After simulation event, facilitators and end-users re-examine the simulation experience, and various aspects of the completed simulation are discussed.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation

Key characteristics in Living Lab context

- Mainly for ICT solutions
- Simulation labs, smart home that simulate real-life home/specific scenarios to simulate real space

Objectives:

- Simulate real-life situations and behavior but lower cost,
- Identify improvement suggestions and usability test,
- Provide development recommendations based on user/patient/customer experience and needs,
- Identify key measures to investigate in follow-up tests

Methods: Simulation test, virtual reality (VR), usage scenarios, interview, debriefing, observation, survey, Wizard of Oz, sensors, usage logs, hospital ward, interactive patient mannequin, usage scenarios

Tools: Audio recording, video recording

4.7.17 Clinical trials

Description: Clinical trials are experiments or observations done to evaluate the effectiveness and safety of new solution by monitoring its effects on large groups of people. Subjects are typically divided into two or more groups, one having “real treatment” by using the developed solution and the other group(s) using tried-and-true solution or not using any solution. The results are compared between the groups to evaluate the impacts.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Clinical trials are similar to impact assessment and validation test activities but follow more strict validation and approval process.

Participants' role:

- Customers as co-creators

Objectives

- To find out if new solutions are safe and effective
- Get official approval for new solution

Methods:

- Has multiple phases and classes which depend on the developed solution

4.7.18 Grant writing and funding application support service

Description: Offering tailored support by identifying the proper local, regional, national and international funding instruments, helping to write and manage a funding application process including finding the right partners for the project if needed. In most cases a Living Lab will become a project partner, but it can also be provided as a paid service without participation.

R&D service category-ies: Advisory services

Objectives:

- Acquiring/providing funding for “customer” to execute a Living lab project or buy Living Lab services,
- Getting project partner for a Living Lab project

4.7.19 Panel management

Description: Panel is a pre-existing group of pre-screened people (e.g. patients, practitioners etc.) who have given their consent to take part in different research activities over an agreed period. Panel members have given their contact details and other profiling information, which enables fast recruitment for specific research activities as they come up.

R&D service category-ies: Community and network building, Project planning and management, Advisory services, Infrastructure and data management

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Group of patients, students but also experts, experts by experience and other staff can be used as a panel (agreement is necessary in every case)
- Having engagement procedures in place (win to win situation), social activities

Objectives:

- Enable fast participant recruitment,
- Lower the management effort (no need to fill profile information multiple times)

Method: survey, recruitment collaboration with medical professionals (e.g., in hospital ward)

Tools/Online tools: intake questionnaire, phone, open calls in social media/web, posters, email, personal invitations

4.7.20 Post-market surveillance and market acceptance testing

Description: Post-market surveillance is a “real world” test of medical innovations in patient subgroups. It is a practice of monitoring the safety of a medical innovation after it has been released on the market. Market acceptance testing focuses on collecting market feedback for the next revision development and tracking the solution performance in real competitive market conditions.

R&D service category-ies: Market and sales support

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Usually within a clinical or community research context (within the context of specific projects/the products that come out as research outcomes) and not as a standalone service.
- As normal customer feedback collection and health promotion, for continuum improvement of the tool

Objectives:

- Monitoring the safety of a medical innovation after it has been released on the market,
- Evaluate social impact,
- Identify new opportunities for business and research

Methods: Survey, observation, interviews, helpdesk logs, technical logs, complain reports, pre and post measurement (long term), market studies

Tools/online tools: questionnaires, validated scientific scale/questionnaires, sensors

4.7.21 Temporary research funding

Description: Providing funding (or an investment) for research, product and business development for small and medium-sized companies or start-ups. Typically, funding is targeted for short-term small-scale experiments or if an externally funded project has resources for this kind of activity (e.g., open calls). Also, it can be done in collaboration with local research centers, publicly funded “development companies” and networks or similar.

R&D service category-ies: Advisory services

Objectives:

- Providing funding to execute small scale Living Lab project (e.g., testing)

Methods: Offering funds within funded projects for small-scale testing or co-creation

4.7.22 Access to data

Description: Referring to service, which enables customers to access or retrieve data from one or more databases consisting of relevant data, based on mutual agreements respecting ethics and GDPR, which can be used for development or testing purposes.

R&D service categories: Testing and validation, Market and sales support, Infrastructure and data management

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Usually 2 sources: already existing data, new data collected
- Data must be anonymized and encrypted
- Consent from participants have been previously acquired by the LLs when it's required by ethical and legal legislations
- Type of data: demographics/personal data, health-clinical data (e.g., cognitive, treatment changes, physical performance, care to rehabilitation), measure data, sensors' data (brain activity)
- For open data, FAIR data principles should be followed
- Ethical approval and GDPR processes when needed

Pre-tasks:

- Create a database to store data
- Define the accessibility of the database (public or limited access) and how data are collected (in an integrated way or occasional/ad hoc databases/infrastructures)
- It is, usually, needed a request that is passed to the responsible of databases

4.7.23 Marketing and sales support

Description: Providing marketing and sales support for 1) making right contacts by giving business contacts, sales and business leads, 2) setting up and arranging meetings and events, 3) showcasing products and services in a showroom or giving online/onsite visibility in Living Lab own communication channels, 4) providing “user approved” certification, and 5) offering soft landing support to help to set up business in given Living Lab country or region.

R&D service category-ies: Market and sales support

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- It can be introductory to healthcare companies and service providers and goes up to the point of developing a BM

Objectives:

- Finding right contacts and customers for Living Lab clients,

Tools: “user approved” certification, showroom, showcasing, business meetings, interviews, events, soft landing services, sales/business leads

4.7.24 Public procurement support services

Description: Public procurement (e.g., related to research activities) is governed by EU and national rules. Support with public contract issues and the public procurement process is given to help clients to meet the tendering criteria and/or join the tendering process. Also helping public authorities to establish market dialogue when developing the public procurement announcement. This includes Pre-Commercial Procurement and innovative procurement processes.

R&D service category-ies: Community and network building

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Pre-commercial procurement, innovative procurement, public procurement
- Project based
- Validation Software (integration) - Hardware (operational validation in real environment)
- Legal design and decision-making support

Methods: Planning process based on co-creation, pre-commercial procurement (PCP), innovative procurement

4.7.25 Equipment and facility rental service

Description: Offering equipment, labs, spaces, human resources and other facilities for rent. Some Living Labs do this based on a win-to-win agreement where money does not change hand. Also, some Living Labs require research collaboration when renting.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and Validation, Co-creation, Advisory services, Infrastructure and data management

Participants’ role: In some cases, researchers can visit the LL and use the provided facilities free of charge

Objectives:

- Getting temporary human, space, technical or other facility resources,
- Enable research collaboration

Methods: Payment, research collaboration grounded on Living Lab resources

Tools: Simulation lab

4.7.26 Foresighting (trends, weak signals and wild cards)

Description: Foresighting is a practice of exploring expected and alternative futures. Trend is a general tendency or direction evident from past events increasing or decreasing in strength of frequency of observation. A weak signal is an indicator of a potentially emerging issue that may become significant in the future. “Wild card” is a high-impact event that seem too incredible or is considered too unlikely to happen; yet many do happen.

R&D service category-ies: Market and sales support

Objectives:

- Policy consulting,
- Create a future vision,
- Identify new opportunities and risks,

Methods: Back casting, brainstorming, user/citizen panels, workshop/session, expert panel, interview, literature review, role playing, scenarios, survey, SWOT, wild card & weak signals, science fiction/crazy ideas

4.7.27 Legal, regulation and safety standard support

Description: Providing support to navigate to the legal, regulatory and safety standard requirements and help planning to meet the requirements.

R&D service category-ies: Advisory services

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Legal design and decision-making support
- Support on signed agreements, protocol
- In some cases, external contractors for IPR, RGDPDR

Objectives:

- Similar to expert opinion and advisory services but focusing on legal and regulatory issues

4.8 PART 6. Living lab research infrastructure

In regulation 1291/2013, the EU Parliament and Council of the EU define Research Infrastructure (RI) as “facilities, resources and services that are used by the research communities to conduct research and foster innovation in their fields”. Living lab RIs consist

- **Single-sited facility:** Unified single body of equipment at one physical location
 - Laboratory or smart home
- **Distributed facility:** Facilities, resources and services that are geographically scattered in multiple location
 - City, city district, outdoor space (e.g., nature/hiking trails)
 - sensor networks, network of homes
- **Virtual access-based facility:** Resources and services that are exclusively available via online internet-based tools.
 - Access and ability storage scientific data and repositories, tools for virtual collaboration, various computer services,
- **Mobile facility:** Facilities and resources which can be easily moved to from one place to another
 - Handheld devices and non-handheld equipment

4.9 PART 7A. Methods and tools

This section includes two templates that can be used as a tool for the designing and reporting of co-creation sessions within the LLs. In particular, the first template consists of several parts that are crucial for thoroughly describing the design and the implementation of a co-creation session and the second one includes the information considered important for reporting it. In addition, this section encompasses three distinct Ethics Tools, namely a protocol template designed for co-creation activities, another protocol template tailored for intervention studies, and a third template for Data Sharing Agreement / Joint-Controller Agreement.

4.9.1 Template for designing a co-creation session

CO-CREATION SESSION

JRA (Joint research activity) x

Small-case study name:

Co-creation session with: (e.g., care professionals, patients, informal carers)

General recommendations:

*The objectives and scenarios can be split up: e.g.: 1 session for care professionals & 1 session for patients/informal carers etc. We would advise you to organize separate sessions for professionals and patients/informal carers and also, to adjust and fill the template separately for each group. The set-up is quite similar, but the focus is sometimes different. It is suggested a min of 4 participants and a max of 12. If wanted, you can video tape, as a back-up (*attention to the ethics considerations – videotaping should be included into the consent form).*

Other recommendations:

- o *Delay erodes quality*
- o *Debriefing and reflection with the team (moderator and observer) improves quality*
- o *Keep the research questions in mind*
- o *Stick as close to the data as possible (quotes, words used by participants)*

RESEARCH QUESTIONS & AIM

Describe the research questions and the objectives of the co-creation session, depending on your target group and the information you want to collect.

*Some general research questions can be the same across the different regions, to be able to compare and report some results later on.

e.g.:

Session with health care professionals	Session with participants (e.g., older adults)
What is their current experience with (intervention) technology?	What experiences do the participants have from previous... (possible benefits, difficulties)?
To what extend is technology accepted by the clinicians? (attitude towards technology)	To what extend is the use of technology accepted by the participants for supporting... (benefits, challenges)?

What are the advantages and limitations of using technology during...?	What are the advantages and limitations of using technology during ...?
How do they follow up on their patients?	

*Please structure and enumerate your research questions in order to be easier to report the answers afterwards (Report template: section “Output summary & main findings”).

STAKEHOLDERS

Define all the stakeholders of your co-creation session

- The number of facilitators
- The number of observers/documenters
- The number of participants

STRUCTURE & PLANNED ACTIVITIES

Define the structure of your co-creation session(s), the activities you are planning to include (e.g., open discussions based on pre-defined questions, brainstorming, demonstration of a selected tool)

GUIDING QUESTIONS

Define the questions you are planning to ask the participants.

*Please structure and enumerate your questions in order to be easier to report the answers afterwards (Report template: section “Output summary & main findings”)

*Some overall questions can be the same for a general part across the small-scale studies within the JRAs.

e.g.:

Session with health care professionals

Research question	Guiding questions
What is their current experience with (intervention) technology?	From your previous experience, are there any technological means that are exploited during...? Do you personally use any kind of technology for supporting...?/How do you use technology?
To what extend is technology accepted (attitude towards technology)?	Are you open to use technology? Are your patients open to use technology?
What are the advantages and limitations of using technology during...?	Are there any difficulties or challenges that you think it’s possible to encounter when using technological means during...? Is there anything that you would like to be different or that could be improved?
How do they follow up on their patients?	

Session with participants (e.g., older adults)

Research question	Guiding questions
-------------------	-------------------

What experiences do the participants have from the use of technology so far (possible benefits, difficulties)?	Do you use any kind of technology in...?/ What are your experiences from previous (challenges, benefits)...? What kind of support you think is needed for you to use technology in...?
To what extent is the use of technology accepted by the participants for supporting... (benefits, challenges)?	Are you open and willing to use technology?/ How possible do you think it is for you to use technological means when you...?
What are the advantages and limitations of using technology during ...?	What would be the biggest return for you to use technology during...? Are there any difficulties or challenges that you think it's possible to encounter when using technological means during...?

TOOLS & MATERIAL/RESOURCES

Describe all the tools and materials you are planning to use during your co-creation session(s) (E.g., informed consent to sign for each participant, templates, post-it, pen/pencils, blackboard etc.)

EXPECTED OUTPUTS

Define the expected outcomes of your co-creation session(s) (e.g., current status, needs, challenges, expectations/what is needed to happen in the future)

EVALUATION QUESTIONNAIRE

Here we will define the common participation questionnaires (one for the participants and one for the LL facilitators) that will be used across the study after the end of the co-creation session.

You will find a proposed questionnaire in the last pages of the report template

PLANNED DATE-TIME, SETTING & AGENDA

Define the date, time, place/setting, as well as the activities and their duration within the co-creation session. Indicate also, who will be engaged in each particular slot of the co-creation session. Define the room set-up (e.g., board room style/round table etc.)

e.g.:

Date: Monday 30 May 2022

Time: 12:00-13:30

Place:

Time	Duration	Activity	Team
12:00	10'	Welcome and registration	all
12:10	10'	Presentation	all
12:20	5'	Split participants into tables	table
12:25	5'	Provide the templates and material	table
12:30	40'	Activities/questions - open discussion	table
13:10	15'	Each team presents briefly what was discussed	all

13:25	5'	Questionnaire	all
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4.9.2 Template for reporting a co-creation session

REPORT_CO-CREATION SESSION

LL name	
WP & Small-case study name	
Facilitator(s)	
Observer(s)/documenter(s)	
Date of co-creation session	
Number of participants (total)	

Facilitator team

List the name and the email of the facilitator(s) and the observers(s)/documenter(s) involved in the session. Indicate their role in the session and their profile (e.g. psychologist, nurse, occupational therapist, physiotherapist, gerontologist etc.)

Participants' profile

Fill in each participant's profile in a different row, checking the appropriate cell.

Serial number	GENDER			Age Year of birth	PROFILE (define the stakeholders you will engage)		
	Male	Female	Neutral / Other		Stakeholder 1	Stakeholder 2	Stakeholder 3
1							
2							
3							
4							
5							
6							
7							

8								
9								
10								
11								
12								

Serial number	Education level								
	ISCED 0: Early childhood education	ISCED 1: Primary education	ISCED 2: Lower secondary education	ISCED 3: Upper secondary education	ISCED 4: Post-secondary non-tertiary education	ISCED 5: Short-cycle tertiary education	ISCED 6: Bachelor's or equivalent level	ISCED 7: Master's or equivalent level	ISCED 8: Doctoral or equivalent level
1									
2									
3									
4									
5									
6									
7									
8									
9									
10									
11									
12									

Serial number	Technology literacy				Previous contact with VITALISE project	
	Basic	Intermediate	Advanced	Excellent	YES	NO
1						
2						
3						
4						
5						
6						
7						
8						

9						
10						
11						
12						

ONLY FOR THE HEALTHCARE PROFESSIONALS

Serial number	How many years have you been in practice?	What area of speciality do you currently work in (i.e. neurology, musculoskeletal etc.)
1		
2		
3		
4		
5		
6		
7		
8		
9		
10		
11		
12		

Session goals

Briefly describe the objectives of the co-creation session.

List of questions & activities

List and briefly describe the questions / activities that guided the discussion for collecting value insights from the participants.

List of tools and materials used

List and briefly describe the list of tools and materials used during the co-creation session.

Output summary & main findings

Give the output summary of the session, including, if possible, 4 main topics: current status, needs, challenges, expectations. You can also include the exceptions, the remarkable examples, and experiences, /how the participants felt. If possible, you can also register relevant quotes/insights from participants.

Topic XX: Main findings:
Topic XX: Main findings:

Incidents

Mention and briefly describe here any possible incidence that occurred during the co-creation session that wasn't planned to happen or hasn't been foreseen. If possible, mention also how you handled it / how you adjusted to this unexpected condition.

--

Photos

In this section add some photos of the event (5-6). It is nice to have some photos depicting the whole event, e.g., with the tables, hands, materials etc., including also the participants, IF THEY HAVE CONSENTED, (probably blurred *ethics considerations). Also, please try to include some photos that have the VITALISE logo in the background (e.g. from a presentation, a banner).

Questionnaire output

In this Section report the output of the VITALISE participation questionnaire (ANNEX 1). This questionnaire is filled by the participants of the co-creation session. Each participant could write his/her name if he/she wants and the facilitator must report the profile category (older adult, caregiver, clinician) for whom they have provided their names an N/A for those have not.

Profile	1	2	3	4	5
	Choose an item.	Choose an item.			
	Choose an item.	Choose an item.			
	Choose an item.	Choose an item.			
	Choose an item.	Choose an item.			
	Choose an item.	Choose an item.			

Happiness of the team

This questionnaire is filled by the Living Lab (facilitators) team. The goal is to record possible problems in the procedure, the communication and the assigned work. Each Living Lab should fill only one questionnaire that depicts the average impression of the whole team.

1. Assign a score from 1-5 in each co-creation session:

Co-creation session	
How do you feel about the amount of work assigned to you in this co-creation session?	
How do you feel about the amount of work you did in this co-creation session?	
How do you feel about the quality/value of work you did in this co-creation session?	

2. What would you change? (Free text response)

3. What did you like more? (Free text response)

ANNEX 1

1. How do you feel about this co-creation session?

2. Would you like to be with us in possible next sessions? YES NO

3. What did you like most on this co-creation session?

.....

.....

.....

.....

.....

One of the most frequently encountered difficulties affecting the [aspect of life], is the [integration/inclusion etc.] of the people [in the target population]. Technological interventions and approaches, in the effort to find a solution, end up being transformed into interventions "from above". Often, therefore, in situations that arise, the needs of people [in the target group] are neglected. An important body of evidence suggests that program designers and programmers have [medium/little or no knowledge] of the challenges that [the target population] faces. [Describe use cases, homogeneity of the target group and existing solutions/methodologies failing to capture them]

In this context, the main objective of the project is:

To gather and utilize interdisciplinary research knowledge and findings that approach the issue of the relationship between [mention the challenges] and [aspect of life]. In this context, it aims to collect data, through spaces of experimentation that provide the potential of action, in order to support [the accessibility/education/interaction etc.] of [the target population], adapting to the individual needs and the necessary settings required for the ["smooth adaptation", "digital transition", etc.] during their [daily/weekly etc.] interaction with [(purpose-specific) software/services].

2. Purpose of study

The purpose of this study is to collect data from the experiences of people with [target population characteristics]. The data that will be collected through interviews and focus groups, will be analyzed to create the framework [for the development of a service/software] with [the purpose of]. The project aims to facilitate participants and people with [target population characteristics] in their interaction [this aspect of life]. At the same time, it aims to identify effective solutions together with individuals through their participation in collaborative and co-design activities. The co-design will take place in the [number of] workshops of the partners of the [project name] project consortium [(Country 1 – Partner 1, Country 2 – Partner 2 etc.)] providing information and suggestions for corrections and modifications regarding [aspect of life under study].

3. Study environment

The data for the study framework will be collected by the research team of the [project name] project, collaborators of the [partner 1 institution, research center 2 institution].

4. Timeline

The study will take place over a period [of duration], between [start date] and [end date].

5. Participants

The participants will be people who have been diagnosed with [syndrome, disorder, disease, healthy etc. – The target population]. These will be indicated by the study partners and their participation will take place under the conditions that they themselves have agreed and that the consent form is signed, [by them or their caregivers/legal representatives if applicable], allowing the collection and processing of data for the study purposes.

The criteria for inclusion of study participants are:

(a) [age criteria].

b) [diagnoses or difficulties which are part of the diagnoses]

c) have the intention to interact and share their experiences regarding the scenarios examined in the context of the [project name] project. These scenarios are related to [aspect of life concerned].

Regarding the exclusion criteria:

Persons outside the age group of [15-44 years] years will be excluded from participating in the study. People, who are likely to face difficulties during their participation such as [mention here difficulties], will be excluded. [In some cases, it may be desirable and useful for a participant's experiences to be provided on their behalf or assisted in their expression by a caregiver of the individual – if applicable].

Interviews / focus groups

Interviews/focus groups will be conducted in two phases, not necessarily with the participation of the same people. The participants of each phase will be:

a) in the first phase, a total of [number of people] in interviews and focus groups (e.g. focus group of 15 people and 15 individual interviews) concerning [aspect of life]

b) in the second phase, a total of [number of people] people in interviews / focus groups that will be held before and after using [the software/service], which aim to facilitate the [aspect of life], for the collection of evaluation data and feedback on the [software/service].

6. Data collection plan

The collection of the data will take place in the context of interviews / focus groups, during which, information will be collected on the usability of [software/services], common problems faced by [the target population] in its interaction with them and their requirements. Each interview is expected to last about [duration] and the focus group about [duration].

The interviews/focus groups may be recorded, and the recordings will be used solely for transcription of the data, without its further disclosure, and a pseudonymization process will follow. Transcripts from the [number of] interviews/ focus groups of the first phase will be sent, upon request, to the research team leading their analysis, [partner 1]. Transcripts from the [number of] interviews/ focus groups related to the [software/service] will be sent, upon request, [partner 1, research center 2].

Regarding the participation: a) the data collected will be solely used for the study purposes, while, in case they are used in published reports, outside the project context, they will be fully anonymized, b) the transcripts of the study will be carried out safely by the research team responsible for the project, and the resulting data will be [deleted/anonymized], on [date of data deletion/anonymization], c) the participants have the right to request for rectification or deletion of personal data at any time before their [deletion/anonymization] date and d) withdrawal from the interview is possible at any time, without requiring justification and without the legal rights of the departee being affected by it.

For more information on participating or to inform the research team of an impending departure from the study, please send an email to [Data Protection Officer email/contact details].

6.1. Data collection process through interview/focus group

The interviews / focus groups will take place [online and/or in person]. Initially, the participant will be welcomed, they will be reminded that their participation is voluntary and that their consent is necessary for the continuation of the process. After signing the consent form, the name of the participant will be converted into a code, which will be used from this point forward, and [the age, diagnosis, educational level, the city of residence, the profession, the period since the onset of their disorder – remove whatever is not applicable] will be collected.

Then, the interview / focus group will commence, stating that there are no wrong answers or views, that all opinions and experiences are acceptable and legitimate, and desirable to be heard. The researchers who will supervise / motivate / conduct and participate in the discussion, will take care, so that the discussion is not monopolized by a few participants, **in the case of a focus group.**

In the first phase of interviews / focus groups, participants will be invited to discuss the quality of [the aspect of life]. In the context of the discussion or interview, the challenges faced in [the aspect of life] and solutions that could offer improvements in it but also in their quality of life, will be analyzed and discussed.

In the second phase of the interviews / focus groups concerning the [software/service], the participants will have the opportunity to use it. This [software/service] will include [software/service content description]. The participants will have to interact with the [software/service] for a short period of time [some minutes], interacting freely with, while afterwards, they will also execute some tasks. Finally, they will have to express their opinion to the research team about the [software/service] functionality and the degree to which it helped them to interact, as well as to suggest possible modifications or additions.

The discussions and interviews that will take place are semi-structured, meaning that there is a precompiled interview draft (chapter 9), but both the interviewer or facilitator of the focus group may deviate from this structure, depending on the answers received and the course of the discussion, within the research design and purpose framework, as new questions are likely to arise, in order to achieve the unhindered expression of the thoughts, ideas and experiences of the participants.

Finally, the researchers will thank the participants.

7. Analyses

7.1. Description of data analysis

i) The analysis of the data collected in the first interviews / focus groups will take place in 3 stages: a) Content analysis of individual interviews and focus groups, b) Comparison and integration of content analysis in reports c) Comparison and integration of reports collected from the project consortium, in the overall project analysis report.

For the first step, the researchers will identify key topics of the discussions and recurring patterns that present and reflect problems faced by [the target population] and they will support their finding, e.g., quoting a phrase or excerpt from the conversation.

To complete the second step, the researchers will incorporate the findings into a report while in the third step, [Partner 1] will perform the same process, summarizing the individual reports of the partners.

ii) The analysis of the second phase interviews / focus groups data will be carried out in the context of the feedback received on the produced [software/service]. The interaction with the [software/service] and its use, through its pilot test, aims to result in a discussion with each participant, which will allow the [software/service] to be evaluated, and the possible issues that arise in its design and usability to be demonstrated. This will provide the [software/service] creators with the necessary and appropriate data, for the development of new improved versions through this co-creation process.

8. Provisions for the ethical conduct of the study

All participants will be informed through an information sheet, which will describe extensively and in a communicatively understandable way (to this audience) the overall study process. Their participation in the study will be made possible only after they provide their written consent, after being informed. The document used for this purpose is the '**Participant Informed Consent Form**'.

Specifically, they will be informed about the purpose of the study and that:

1. Their participation is voluntary and not obligatory.
2. They can ask any question about the study before deciding to participate in it.
3. They will be made aware of the individual and group benefits from their participation.
4. They will be informed of the exact way of collection, transfer and protection of sensitive personal data during the project, as well as its subsequent processing and utilization of these data, whether for example they will be deleted or reused, if such will be the case.
5. They will receive detailed and complete information, and that their consent is required for participating in the study, as well as for any further processing of their data.
6. They will be informed that they are able, at any time, to withdraw from the study or to request their data to be deleted, without consequences, and without affecting the services they receive by [their research doctor / health provider etc.].
7. Each participant's informed consent form will include the contact details of both the investigator's who conducted the briefing and those of the study principal investigator's.
8. The copy of the provided informed consent form will explicitly state that this information has been submitted to the [Research Ethics and Deontology Committee of [Partner 1]] beforehand and that all personal information and sensitive personal data will have been [pseudonymized with unique identification numbers / anonymized]

Appendices

Questionnaire – Interview / focus group guidelines

The interviews / focus groups will be based, but not restricted, on the following guidelines:

1. The date, time, location and number of the participants (if it is a focus group) of the meeting are noted.
2. The participants test the [software/service], provided by the research team.
3. The participants will interact with the [software/service], by performing free actions, but also specific tasks given by the research team.
4. The team will note difficulties and problems in using the [software/service].
5. Clarifying questions that stimulate the discussion, regarding [software/service] usability, will follow:
 - "Do you think the [service/software] facilitates your [aspect of life]?"
 - "Did you have difficulty using it? / If so, do you have anything specific to mention? / What were they? / How could they be improved?"
 - "What functions of the [service/software], do you think / consider / evaluate to be more useful and which ones less? / Why?"
 - "If you could add other function(s), what would they be?"

4.9.3.2 Protocol template for intervention studies

(for studies that do not involve medicines or medical devices according to EU 536/2014 & EU 2017/745-746)

(Highlighted text is present to provide examples. Please replace it to correspond to your study)

STUDY NAME:

Principal Investigator:

Contact information:

Data Protection Officer:

<p>1. Subject of the study and its objectives; state the hypotheses, separated into main and secondary hypotheses, and the clinical parameters (primary and secondary endpoints) against which the hypotheses will be tested</p>	<p>Study summary:</p> <p>Study Purpose:</p> <p>For this purpose, the study must be divided into sub-steps: Data acquisition, data collection, and statistical analysis.</p> <p>Data Acquisition: WHAT (end-points/outcome measures) is/are going to be measured</p> <p>Statistical analysis:</p> <p>Data will be analyzed using R/SPSS/Python/{name of other}. Name the statistic tests to be used for each category of data described above. A p-value below 0.05 is considered statistically significant.</p> <p>Hypotheses:</p> <p>Hypothesis 1:</p>
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	Hypothesis 2: ...
2. Study timeline	Recruitment starts: D/M/YYYY Recruitment ends: D/M/YYYY Last participant exits: D/M/YYYY Data analysis starts: D/M/YYYY Data analysis ends: D/M/YYYY Or estimated period e.g., October 2020 till May 2023
3. Explanation of the significance of the study	
4. Which of the following regulations, laws, codes of conduct or other apply	a) EU 679/2016 b) Declaration of Helsinki c) The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, 2017 d) OTHER (e.g., EU 745/2017, 536/2014, national implementations of GDPR etc.)
5. Description of the planned measures/examination methods and any deviations from the measures/examinations commonly used in medical practice (what is "routine", what is done differently in the study?) -If validated questionnaires are used for study purposes, please indicate the name of the questionnaires and where they are published (references). -Please attach non-validated questionnaires.	Describe what the study entails and what is going to be measured Data collection: HOW, WHEN, WHERE, STORAGE Questionnaire #1, reference Questionnaire #2, reference Attach non-validated questionnaires as appendix
6. Evaluation and weighing of the foreseeable risks and disadvantages of study participation against the expected benefits for the study participants and persons who will become ill in the future (risk-benefit balance).	Remove row if not applicable (e.g., use of questionnaires)
a. Medical benefit to be tested for the study participants (individual benefit for the individual patient).	Remove row if not applicable (e.g. use of questionnaires) (e.g., There is no individual benefit to the study participants from completing the questionnaire.)

b. Medical benefit to be tested for persons with the disease in the future (group benefit).	What is the benefit to society/patients/future patients if the proposed study is successful
c. Risks and burdens to study participants (list all in detail).	List of risks or There are no risks for the study participants.
7. Measures to control risks	List of measures or There are no risks for the study participants.
8. Termination criteria	e.g., Recruitment numbers have been reached, project duration is up
9. Number, age, and sex of the persons concerned	
10. Power analysis with indication of statistical methodology, including justification of the number of cases. Specification of the statistician (if applicable)	WHO is going to perform the analysis (e.g., researcher, physician or NAME SURNAME of statistician) A power analysis was performed to estimate the sample size. At $\alpha=0.05$ and power= 0.80 , the extrapolated sample size required to detect a small effect (Cohen $d=0.2$) for between/within-group comparisons was $N=787$. Therefore, the inclusion of at least 787 subjects was deemed necessary.
11. a. Presentation and explanation of the inclusion and exclusion criteria , if applicable	
b. Study information (who gives verbally and in writing an indication of how much time is left between information and consent (written information as an attachment)?)	Who informs the participants. How much time is left between information and consent
c. Declaration of consent (written form as attachment)	The information sheet and consent form is attached to this application. Each participant receives a copy of the information sheet and the consent form.
d. If applicable, information and consent of the legal representative (if applicable, also description of the procedure for the establishment of judicial care for subjects unable to consent).	Remove row if not applicable

12. Measures to recruit study participants (notice board, newspaper advertisements, etc.)	
13. If applicable: reason for inclusion and demonstration of therapeutic benefit for individuals who are minors and/or unable to consent.	Remove row if not applicable
14. Relationship between study participant and study researcher/physician (is the study physician also the treating physician?).	Remove row if not applicable
15. Statement on the involvement of persons possibly dependent on the sponsor.	Remove row if not applicable
16. Measures that allow a determination of whether a study participant is participating in multiple studies at the same time or before the expiration of a period specified in the previous study. Is participation in multiple studies possible?	Remove row if not applicable
17. If applicable: remuneration or reimbursement of study participants (amount, for what should be paid?)	Remove row if not applicable
18. If applicable: insurance of the study participants (confirmation of insurance and insurance conditions, insurer, scope of insurance, duration of insurance).	The study is covered by the public/private liability insurance of the [name_of_insurance_provider]. Remove row if not applicable.
19. Documentation procedure: -Reference to CRF sheets, if applicable -Indication of the data to be collected -Sample handling -Retention/archiving (incl. deadlines) -Access to the data and/or samples	The research data collected from the patient/participant will be digitized into REDCap/OpenClinica/Other server using specific codes/standards which is located in [institution/(cloud)storage provider]-internal servers and kept for X years/months, after which the data will be anonymized/deleted. WHO will have access?
20. If applicable: description of how the health status of healthy affected persons is to be documented	Remove row if not applicable

<p>21. If applicable: methods to identify, document and report adverse events (when, by whom and how?)</p>	<p>Remove row if not applicable</p>
<p>22. Procedure to protect the confidentiality of stored data, documents, and, if applicable, samples, presentation of pseudonymization or anonymization of data, and samples of study participants (initials and date of birth as coding scheme are not allowed!).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Description of the separation of medical records, study documentation, and allocation of personal data. -Identification of access rights, including access to participant identification lists, during and after study implementation. -Detailed indication of the procedures for transmission, encryption, restriction of processing (blocking) and deletion (including an indication of the network structure used, if any, and servers used). -If necessary, access to identifying data for legally authorized auditors (third parties) for purpose-bound inspection of the files required for this purpose. 	<p>Strict compliance with EU 2016/679 (or other national laws) is ensured.</p> <p>Provide information according to the list on the left row</p>
<p>23. Declaration of compliance with data protection.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Assurance that all data collected and stored about the study participant will be treated confidentially (data secrecy and medical confidentiality). -Assurance that the identifying data are accessible only to the study director or to employees authorized by the study director. 	<p>Participating physicians of the [LOCATION] are obliged to observe data secrecy and medical confidentiality. Researchers have signed Non-Disclosure Agreements (NDA). The data will not be passed on to third parties.</p> <p>e.g., pseudonymization, appointment of DPO, access control, encryption and more</p>

<p>-Indication of the measures taken to ensure confidentiality.</p> <p>-Measures for the data-protection-compliant transfer of data that do not allow third parties to establish a personal reference.</p> <p>-Information on the rights of data subjects.</p> <p>-Measures to ensure the rights of participants.</p> <p>-If transfers to non-EU countries are planned: Are data protection compliance measures in place (e.g., existence of an adequacy decision by the EU Commission or explicit consent of study participants to such transfers)?</p>	
<p>24. Names and addresses of the institutions involved in the study as study centers or study laboratories, as well as the study directors and the study physicians.</p> <p>- Specification of involved external service provider with indication of data access possibility.</p>	<p>Include applicable roles:</p> <p>Study Director/Principal Investigator:</p> <p>Researchers:</p> <p>Physicians:</p> <p>Statistician:</p> <p>Other:</p> <p>Name and address of institution(s):</p>
<p>25. Information on the suitability of the trial site, in particular, on the adequacy of the resources and facilities available there, as well as on the personnel available to conduct the clinical trial and on experience in conducting similar trials.</p>	<p>The department of [LOCATION] and the scientists involved in this project have many years of experience in academic work and publications in high-ranking medical and technical journals.</p> <p>e.g., The [lab/Department/centre/other] is one of the most research-intensive departments at [LOCATION/UNIVERSITY etc.] and one of the most research-intensive [LAB/Department/centre/other] in [COUNTRY].</p>
<p>26. Agreement on access of the investigator/principal investigator/leader of the study to the data and the principles on publication.</p> <p>- Publications in a form that does not allow any conclusions to be drawn about the person.</p>	<p>Publication policy:</p> <p>Declaration that data included in publication are aggregates.</p> <p>[Only for VITALISE TA] Data Access and Publication policy is described in the “VITALISE Agreement for Transnational Access to Research Infrastructures” and the “VITALISE Transnational Bilateral User Agreement” signed by the Living Lab infrastructure provider and the Transnational Access user.</p>

27. Information on the funding of the study: funding source (name and location) and amount of funding in €.	
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4.9.3.3 Template for Data Sharing Agreement / Joint-Controller Agreement

Data Sharing Agreement / Joint-Controller Agreement

Version 1.0 as of [month, year]

“[Research project full name]”

(“the Project”),

[(if a Grant Agreement is in place)

as identified in the Grant Agreement]

[project number – short name]

Between

[name of Living Lab 1]

[name of Living Lab 2]

...

[name of Living Lab 3]

Parties to the Agreement

This Agreement is between:

Organisation / Living Lab	Represented by
European Network of Living Labs (ENOLL)	[Insert name, surname and job title here of person with the signing authority for the organization e.g., CEO, President, Rector etc.]

The Parties are acting as joint controllers on behalf of the [short name] research project which has received funding from [funding authority/programme] under [Grant/Bilateral/Other] Agreement No [project number], entitled: “[Project full name]”.

The Parties agree to share the Personal Data on terms set out in this Agreement which explains the purposes for which that Personal Data may be used.

In the context of the specific project, all parties can act as data providers and/or data recipients.

AGREED TERMS

1. INTERPRETATION

The following definitions and rules of interpretation apply in this agreement.

Definitions:

Privacy and Data Protection Legislation: The national data protection legislation, the Human Rights Act 1998, the European Convention on Human Rights, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR; EU 2016/679) and all applicable laws and regulations relating to the processing of the personal data and privacy, and the equivalent of any of the foregoing in any relevant jurisdiction. References to legislation include any amendments made to those laws from time to time.

The Project: The [project short name] project.

Agreed Purposes: has the meaning given to it in Clause 3 of this Agreement.

The Agreement: this Agreement.

Business Day: a day other than a Saturday, Sunday or public holiday in the countries of each Party when banks are open for business.

The Tasks: the tasks the Parties are contracted to carry out under the [Grant/Bilateral/Other] Agreement No [project number] in order to provide the relevant deliverables.

Joint Controllers: According to Article 26(1) GDPR where two or more controllers jointly determine the purposes and means of processing of personal data, they shall be joint controllers.

Data provider: means the Party acting as joint controller, whose role in the Project involves the provision of personal data to the Project, including data transferring to the Data Recipients, for the purposes and tasks set out in [project number] and further specified in Appendix I to this Agreement.

Data recipient(s): means one (or more) of the Parties, acting as joint controller(s), whose role in the Project involves research and analysis on personal data provided to the Project by the Data Provider, for the purposes and tasks set out in the [reference in the project] of the Project [Grant/Bilateral/Other] Agreement No [project number] and further specified in Appendix I to this Agreement.

Data Processor: means a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which processes personal data on behalf of a controller.

Lead Data Protection Authority: the supervisor authority of the Data Provider.

The Data Protection Authorities Concerned: the supervisor authorities of the Data Recipients.

The Personal Data: means personal data as defined in the GDPR, any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person, including [define personal data here or in an Appendix] and to be shared between the parties under Clause 4 of this Agreement.

Subject Access Request: means the "Right of access by the data subject" in Article 15 of the GDPR.

Term: shall mean the duration of the data sharing agreement which shall remain in force for the duration of the Project, but until [date], unless an extension of the Project duration is granted by the [funding authority].

Data Subject, Personal Data, sensitive/special category data, pseudonymisation, anonymisation, personal data breach, processing, supervisory authority and appropriate technical and organisational measures shall have the meanings given to them in Article 4 of the GDPR.

Clause, Appendix and paragraph headings shall not affect the interpretation of this Agreement.

The Appendices form part of this Agreement and shall have effect as if set out in full in the body of this Agreement. Any reference to this Agreement includes the Appendices.

Unless the context requires otherwise, words in the singular shall include the plural and, in the plural, shall include the singular.

References to Clauses and Appendices are to the Clauses and Appendices of this Agreement and references to paragraphs are to paragraphs of the relevant Appendix.

Any words following the terms including, include, in particular or for example or any similar phrase shall be construed as illustrative and shall not limit the generality of the related general words.

A reference to **writing** or **written** includes letter, fax and email.

2. COMPLIANCE WITH DATA PROTECTION LAWS

2.1 The Parties acknowledge that under the GDPR, the Parties are acting as Joint Controllers where processing Personal Data under the terms of this Agreement.

2.2 Each Party must ensure compliance with the Privacy and Data Protection Legislation at all times during the Term of the Agreement.

3. AGREED PURPOSES

3.1 This Agreement sets out the framework for the sharing of Personal Data between the Parties. It sets out the purposes for which the Parties, the principles may process the Personal data and procedures that the Parties shall adhere to and the respective responsibilities of the Parties, in a transparent manner.

3.2 In order to carry out the tasks set under the [Grant/Bilateral/Other] Agreement No [project number] the Parties have to transfer Personal Data between the Parties. Appendix I to this Agreement provides a detailed outline of the Purposes and Tasks and how the personal data will be processed to carry out those Tasks related to the purposes of the project.

3.3 The Parties agree to only process the Personal data in accordance with the instructions set out in this Agreement, and only for the purposes of performing the Tasks as described in Appendix I. The Parties shall not process Personal Data in a way that is incompatible with the purposes described in this Clause (the Agreed Purposes).

3.4 Each party shall appoint a single point of contact (SPoC) who will work together to reach an agreement with regards to any issues arising from the data sharing and to actively improve the effectiveness of the data sharing agreement. The points of contact for each of the parties are:

List of Single Point of Contact persons

[Parties, contact persons, contact information]

4. PERSONAL DATA

4.1 The Personal Data shared under this Agreement are [define personal data here or in Appendix III]

4.2 The Parties agree that the Personal Data shared under this Agreement must be pseudonymized by the Data Provider before transferring to Data Recipients and not be irrelevant or excessive with regard to the Agreed Purposes set out in Clause 3, in order to minimise the amount of Personal Data shared, in accordance with the Data Minimisation Principle.

4.3 The Data Recipients agree to process the Personal Data described in [Clause 4.1 or Appendix III], only for the purposes outlined in Clause 3 of this Agreement and strictly for no other purpose without the written authority of the Data Provider.

4.4 The Data Recipients will NOT disclose or share the Personal Data processed under the Agreement, with any third party without the written authority of the Data Provider.

4.5 The Data Recipients are prohibited from publishing any information related or produced by the Personal Data shared, including any results, without prior authorisation by the **Data Provider**.

5. **FAIR, TRANSPARENT AND LAWFUL PROCESSING**

5.1 Each Party shall ensure that it processes the Personal Data in a fair, transparent and lawful manner in accordance with the Privacy and Data Protection Legislation during the Term of this Agreement.

5.2 For the purposes of processing collected data from [project short name] users, as described in Appendix I, to this Agreement, each Party shall ensure that it processes shared Personal Data on the basis of the following legal grounds:

- a. Lawful processing is based on the data subjects' consent according to Article 6(1a) of the GDPR and/or
- b. Lawful processing is based on the public interest and/or
- c. Lawful processing is based on the purposes of the legitimate interests pursued by the joint controllers.

[Define the appropriate basis for lawful processing]

5.3 For the purposes described in Clause 5.2 of this Agreement, the Data Provider undertakes to inform, where applicable, the data subjects with the information listed in Article 13 of the GDPR in order to comply with the principle of transparency.

6. **DATA ACCURACY**

6.1 The Parties agree to ensure that the Personal Data processed is accurate and kept up to date. The Parties agree to review the accuracy of the personal data and make any necessary changes to any Personal Data, which is inaccurate or requires updating.

6.2 Where either Party becomes aware of inaccuracies in shared Personal Data, they will notify the other Parties.

7. **RETENTION PERIOD**

7.1 The Parties shall retain the personal data of data subjects for [define the retention period of data as well as whether they shall be anonymised or deleted afterwards].

8. **DATA SUBJECTS' RIGHTS**

8.1 For the purposes of processing collected data from [project short name] users based on the legal grounds of Clause 5.2 of this Agreement, the Data Subjects are entitled to the following rights:

- a. The right to be informed, the right of access, the right to rectification, the right to data portability and the right to withdraw consent.
- b. In case the consent is withdrawn, the Parties have the obligation to erase the Personal Data that was processed, unless there is another purpose justifying the continued retention . In this case and in line with Articles 7(3), 17(1b), 17(3d) and 89 of the GDPR, the processing of Personal Data necessary for scientific research purposes or for the purposes of archiving in the public interest may be used to justify the retention of the Personal Data.
- c. Any change in the lawful basis for processing must be notified to a Data Subject in accordance with the information requirements in Articles 13 and 14 of the GDPR and under the general principle of transparency.

8.2 Data Subjects can exercise their rights through a Subject Access Request to the Data Provider. If required, the Data Recipients agree to provide full co-operation and assistance to the Data Provider to enable him to comply with Subject Access Requests and to respond to any other queries or complaints. The Data Recipients agree to provide such assistance promptly and no later than [N] Business Days upon receipt by the Data Provider of a Data Subject request.

8.3 In case of any Subject Access Requests, queries or complaints received by the Data Recipients, the Data Recipients shall notify the Data Provider immediately (and no later than [define time period]) upon receipt in order to enable the Data Provider to respond promptly to the Data Subjects.

8.4 The Data Recipients agree to act only under the Data Provider's instructions in relation to any activities undertaken to resolve any complaints or comply with any requests from the Data Subjects under Clause 7.

8.5 To facilitate the Data Subjects' rights, the Parties agree to maintain Records of all Personal Data processed and all processing activities under the Agreement (including any processing activities outsourced to a Data Processor, see Clause 8) in a structured, commonly used and machine-readable form. In addition to the above Records, the Parties shall maintain a record of Subject Access Requests or complaints including the decisions made or measures taken and any information that was exchanged. The Data Provider reserves the right to inspect the records maintained by the Data Recipients under this Clause at any time.

9. **THIRD PARTY ACCESS**

List of third parties

[Legal name, Address, Country] [has appointed a DPO/has a privacy policy in place (link)] and will process the following personal data under commercial terms & conditions: [Personal data 1, Personal data 2, Personal data 3]. All data accessed by [Legal name] will be pseudonymized. Participants will be informed of this third-party access and will have given consent before said access is performed.

10. **DATA TRANSFERS OUTSIDE THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AREA (EEA)**

[List the recipients of personal data outside the EEA and the technical and organisational measures taken or contractual clauses or adequacy decision in place.]

[Legal name, Address, Country] The European Commission published an adequacy decision for the [Country], for the purposes of Art. 45 of EU 2016/679, on [date of decision] which will last, unless renewed, until [date of EC decision's termination].

11. **SECURITY**

11.1 The Parties shall implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to protect the Personal Data shared, in particular from accidental or unlawful destruction, loss, alteration, unauthorised disclosure of, or access to Personal Data transmitted, stored or otherwise processed in accordance with Article 32 of the GDPR.

11.2 Specifically, taking into account the Agreed Purposes and Processing activities (Clause 3), the nature of the Personal Data shared (Clause 4), the state of the art, the costs of implementation, as well as the risks arising from such processing activities for the rights and freedoms of the Data subjects, the Parties shall implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure a level of security appropriate to those risks, including but not limited to the measures specified in Appendix II to this Agreement. The Parties agree to assist each other in meeting their obligation to keep the Personal Data shared secure and notify each other of any changes to the measures described in Appendix II.

11.3 The Data Recipients agree to allow for inspections and assessments to be undertaken by the Data Provider in respect of the security measures taken, or to provide evidence of those measures if requested.

12. **DATA PROTECTION IMPACT ASSESSMENT (DPIA)**

12.1 The Data Recipients as Joint Controllers with the Data Provider shall provide assistance to the Data Provider in meeting Article 35 obligation of the GDPR, if required, to carry out a joint Data Protection Impact Assessment, in relation to Processing of the Personal Data shared and taking into

account any future changes on the risks represented by processing operations that might require a review of the original Data Protection Impact Assessment.

12.2 Where a DPIA referred to Clause 12.1 indicates an unmitigated high risk to the processing operations, the Data Recipients shall assist the Data Provider in meeting the Prior Consultation obligation with its Supervisory Authority in accordance of Article 36 of the GDPR.

13. PERSONAL DATA BREACHES AND REPORTING PROCEDURES

13.1 The Data Recipients are under a strict obligation to immediately notify the Data Provider of any Personal Data Breach and no later than 24 hours upon the Data Recipients' becoming aware of the breach. The Data Recipients shall provide all available information for the breach in order to enable the Data Provider to assess the risks to the rights and freedoms of the Data subjects and the actions required to resolve the issue in accordance with the Privacy and Data Protection Legislation and guidelines.

13.2 In case the Personal Data Breach is likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of the Data Subjects, the Data Recipients shall provide full assistance in order for the Data Provider to notify its Supervisory Authority within 72 hours, and if required, to notify the affected Data Subjects. Taking into account the conditions of the breach and the security measures applied, the Supervisor Authority might decide that a communication of the breach to the Data Subjects, in line with Article 34 of the GDPR, is not required.

13.3 The Data Recipients shall assist the Data Provider to document any Personal Data Breaches, comprising the facts relating to the security breaches, its effects and the remedial action taken to enable the Supervisory Authority to verify compliance with Article 33 of the GDPR.

14. DOCUMENTATION OF COMPLIANCE AND AUDIT RIGHTS

14.1 Upon request by the Data Provider, the Data Recipients shall make available to the Data Provider all relevant information needed to demonstrate that they are all meeting the requirements of the GDPR, and reasonably cooperate with audits, including inspections by the Data Provider or an auditor mandated by the Data Provider or a competent Supervisory Authority. In order to be able to demonstrate compliance the Parties shall maintain appropriate records as described in Clauses 8.5 and 13.3.

14.2 The Data Provider shall give notice of any audit or inspection to be conducted to a Data Recipient and shall make reasonable endeavours to avoid causing damage or disruption to the Data Recipient's premises, equipment and work in the course of such an audit or inspection.

14.3 The Data Recipients must inform immediately the Data Provider in case they think they have been given an instruction, which does not comply with the Privacy and Data Protection Legislation.

15. TERMINATION

15.1 The Parties agree that following expiration or termination of this Agreement, the Data Recipients and any Processor acting on behalf of a Data recipient shall, at the choice of the Data Provider, return all the Personal Data transferred and the copies thereof to the Data Provider or shall destroy all the personal data and certify to the Data Provider that they have done so, unless legislation imposed upon a Data Recipient or any Processor prevents them from returning or destroying all or part of the Personal Data transferred. In that case, the Data Recipients or any Processor engaged must warrant that they shall guarantee the confidentiality of the personal data transferred and shall not actively process the personal data transferred anymore. The terms of this Agreement will continue to apply to such Personal Data.

15.2 The Data Provider reserves the right to issue instructions to be followed by the Data Recipients including any Processors for the destruction of the Personal Data shared under Clause 15.1, at any time.

16. LIMITATION OF LIABILITY

16.1 Nothing in this Agreement relieves the Data Providers and Data recipients as joint controllers of their own direct responsibilities and liabilities under the GDPR.

17. SEVERANCE

17.1 If any provision or part-provision of the Agreement is or becomes invalid, illegal or unenforceable, it shall be deemed modified to the minimum extent necessary to make it valid, legal and enforceable. If such modification is not possible, the relevant provision or part-provision shall be deemed deleted. Any modification to or deletion of a provision or part-provision under this clause shall not affect the validity and enforceability of the rest of this agreement.

18. CHANGES TO THE APPLICABLE LAW

18.1 In case the applicable data protection and ancillary laws change in a way that the Agreement is no longer adequate for the purpose of governing lawful data sharing exercises, the Data Provider reserves the right to amend this Agreement. In such circumstances, the Data Recipients agree to implement any changes to its processing activities as are necessary to comply with the amended terms of the Agreement.

19. FORCE MAJEURE

19.1 Neither Party shall be in breach of this Agreement nor liable for delay in performing, or failure to perform, any of its obligations under this Agreement if such delay or failure result from events, circumstances or causes beyond its reasonable control. In such circumstances, the affected party shall be entitled to a reasonable extension of the time for performing such obligations. If the period of delay or non-performance continues for 3 months, the Party not affected may terminate this Agreement by giving 30 days' written notice to the affected Party.

20. GOVERNING LAW AND DISPUTE RESOLUTION

20.1 This Agreement shall be governed by GDPR. The Clauses shall be governed by the law of the Member State in which the Data provider is established. The Parties will firstly seek to resolve any disputes arising in connection with this Agreement by amicable settlement. The Parties shall abide by a decision of a competent court or of the Lead Supervisory Authority of the Data Provider's country of establishment.

Appendix I – Purposes and Tasks

[Short description of the research project (purpose) with focus in personal data processing (tasks)]

Appendix II – Description of the Security Measures

[Describe security measures for data protection implemented by each party such as Pseudonymisation, Encryption, back-up procedures, Audit Log operation, non-disclosure agreements, non-reidentification declaration, ISO27001 etc]

Appendix III – Description of Personal Data

[Description of what personal data is to be processed in the research project]

SIGNATURES

AS WITNESS:

Each person signing below and each Party on whose behalf such person executes this Agreement warrants that he/she, as the case may be, has the authority and the legal capacity to enter into this Agreement and perform the obligation herein.

The Parties have caused this Data Sharing Agreement to be duly signed by the undersigned authorised representatives in separate signature pages the day and year first above written.

[Organisation/Living Lab 1]

Signature:

Name:

Position:

Date:

[Organisation/Living Lab 2]

Signature:

Name:

Position:

Date:

4.10 PART 7B. Devices and technologies

This Part presents a taxonomy for identifying and classifying the data that are collected in Living Lab environments and consequently link the devices that are used for collecting each data category. The aim of the taxonomy is to help finding the appropriate digital data collection tools for living lab research and/or expand understanding about available tools and their possibilities. Furthermore, the taxonomy aims to facilitate data collection by driving a unified representation schema of the collected datasets enabling the the cross-organizational collaboration and the accessibility of Living Labs to external stakeholders.

Table 20 Devices and technologies provided by Living Labs

			Definition
Categories of devices for data monitoring and collection	Environmental monitoring		characterize and monitor the environment, establish environmental parameters and conditions. As environment we refer to the person's surroundings either indoors or outdoors
	Human monitoring	Biometrics	biological measurements — or physical characteristics — that can be used to identify individuals and their unique characteristics such as fingerprint scanning or voice recognition
		Electrical Biosignals and physiological monitoring measures	electrical biosignals, or bioelectrical time signals, usually refers to the change in electric current produced by the sum of an electrical potential difference across a specialized tissue, organ or cell system like the nervous system
		(Primary) Vital signs	a group of the six most important medical signs that indicate the status of the body's vital function according to HL7 standard

		Body size and composition	measurement of a person's body, used as qualifying elements for vital signs
		Cognitive ability and mental processes	Measuring the processes involved in the acquisition of knowledge, reasoning and management of information and the brain-based skills we need to carry out any task
		Activity and behavioral monitoring	monitoring the individuals' physical activities and tracking their performance. Monitoring behavior and activities of daily living (ADLs)
Categories of technologies for interventions	Assistive Technology		technologies used to increase, maintain, or improve the functional capabilities of individuals, the feeling of autonomy, safety and general wellbeing or also supporting participation.
	Extended reality - XR (VR & AR)		allows for a two-way flow of information through an interface between the user and the technology through a simulated experience that can be similar to or completely different from the real world
	Serious Games		all the digital games that are used as interventions for health and wellbeing not including XR

Table 21 Devices and technologies subcategories

Category	Subcategory
Environment monitoring	Concentration levels (air pollution levels, humidity, atmospheric pressure, air quality)
	Technical alerts (e.g., flood, smoke)
	Environmental Temperature (air or water temperature)
	Luminosity
	Audiovisual devices
Biometrics	Face recognition
	Voice recognition
Electrical and monitoring measures Biosignals and physiological measures	EEG (electroencephalography)
	ECG (electrocardiography)
	EMG (electromyography)
	Vo2 (maximal oxygen consumption)
	Blood oxygen
	Blood sugar level
	GSR (galvanic skin response)
(Primary) Vital signs	Diastolic blood pressure
	Systolic blood pressure
	Heart rate
	Body temperature
	Respiratory rate
	Oxygen saturation
Body size and composition	body height - lying (measure on a horizontal surface)
	body weight
	body measures (fat, mass, muscle, water and bone)
	circumference measures (head, neck, biceps, waist, hip, chest, forearm, thigh and calf)
	Body Mass Index
Cognitive ability and mental processes	cognitive tasks and paradigms
	memory
	processing speed
	attention
Activity and behavioral monitoring and tracking	walking speed
	orientation

	human body location (indoors or outdoors)
	movement monitoring
	human balance
	physical activity level
	physical performance
	sleep
	steps
	stress level
	physical performance
	technology usage habits and patterns
	fall detection
	gesture recognition and detection
Assistive Technology	reminders & alert
	coaching
	training
	walk assistance
	support activities of daily living (ADLs)
	natural language understanding
Extended reality – XR (VR & AR)	Virtual reality (VR)
	Augmented reality (AR)
Serious Games	cognitive gaming
Mobile and Computer Games	physical gaming - exergames
	educational games

4.11 PART 7C Validated Questionnaires and instruments

The following tables summarize the questionnaires and instruments utilized during the JRA pilots and the TA research studies, categorized in four (4) main axes: 1) Health Status & Wellbeing, 2) Cognitive Status, 3) Physical Activity/Mobility, and 4) Usability & User Experience Measures.

Table 22 Health Status & Wellbeing questionnaires and instruments

Health status & Wellbeing	
Variable measured	Tool
Quality of life	World Health Organization quality of life assessment - BREF (WHOQOL -BREF)
	McGill Quality of Life Questionnaire

Quality of life/Health status	EuroQol (EQ-5D)
	12-Item Short Form Survey (SF-12)
	36-Item Short Form Survey (SF-36)
	PROMIS-29
	Menopause rating scale (MRS)
	Stroke-Specific Quality of Life Scale (SS-QOL)
	Healthy Lifestyle Questionnaire (HLQ)
Eating/Swallowing disorders	Eating Assessment Tool (EAT-10)
	Eating Habits Questionnaire
ADHD	Adult ADHD Self-Report Scale (ASRS-v1.1)
Mental wellbeing/Distress	Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-9)
	Geriatric Depression Scale (GDS)
	Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Well-being Scale (WEMWBS)
	State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI)
	General Anxiety Disorder Assessment (GAD7)
	Beck Depression Inventory (BDI)
	Short Anxiety Screening Test (SAST)
	Stress Visual Analog Scale (VAS Stress)
	Well-Being Index (WHO-5)
	Perceived Stress Scale (PSS)
	Basic Psychological Need Satisfaction and Frustration Scale (BPNSFS)
	Depression, Anxiety Stress Scale (DASS-42)
	Mental wellbeing/Self-efficacy/Self-determination
Behavioural Regulation in Exercise Questionnaire-2 (BREQ-2)	

Loneliness and Isolation	University of California Los Angeles Loneliness Scale (UCLA 3-item)
	Lubben Social Network Scale (LSNS-6)
Fatigue	Multidimensional Fatigue Inventory (MFI)
	Fatigue Likert scale
	Fatigue Visual Analog scale (VAS Fatigue)
Burnout	Academic Burnout Scale
Pain	Pain Visual Analog Scale (VAS Pain)
	McGill pain questionnaire
Autonomy & Control / Functional status	Lawton Instrumental Activities of Daily Living (Lawton IADL)
Frailty	Clinical Frailty Scale (CFS)
Mortality prediction	Charlson Comorbidity Index (CCI)

Table 23 Cognitive status questionnaires and instruments

Cognitive status	
Variable measured	Tool
Multiple cognitive processes/Cognitive impairment	Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA)
	Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE)
Attention and Processing skills	Stroop Test
Verbal learning and Memory	Hopkins Verbal Learning Test (HVLT)
Attention, sequencing, visual search, psychomotor speed	Trail Making TestA + B
Working memory, attention, sequencing	Digit span (Forward and Backward)
Psychomotor speed	Symbol-Digit Modalities Test (SDMT)
Executive cognitive function	Functional cognitive assessment scale (FUCAS)

Table 24 Physical Activity/Mobility questionnaires and instruments

Physical Activity/Mobility	
Variable measured	Tool
Intensity levels of physical activity	Community Healthy Activities Model Program for Seniors (CHAMPS)
	Borg Perceived exertion Scale
Time spent for different levels physical activity	International Physical Activity Questionnaire (IPAQ)
Physical activity level, strength, flexibility	Rapid Assessment of Physical Activity (RAPA)
Physical impairment and activity of an individual following a stroke	Chedoke-McMaster Stroke Assessment (CMSA)
Persons' perception of balance and stability during activities of daily living and their fear of falling	Tinetti-test
Static balance and fall risk	Berg Balance Scale (BBS)
Leg strength and endurance	30" Chair Stand Test
Lower body flexibility	Chair sit-and-reach test / Chair stand test
Fall risk and the progress of balance, sit to stand and walking	Timed Up & Go (TUG)
Aerobic capacity and endurance	2-Minute Step test
	6 Minute Walk Test
Self-paced walking ability and functional capacity	2 Minute Walk Test
Speed in meters per second	10 Metre Walk Test
Finger dexterity	9-hole peg test
Functional Balance	Mini Balance Evaluation Systems Test (Mini-BEST Test)
Balance and gait while backwards walking	Backward walking test

Static postural and balance control	Balance on one leg / Single leg Stand test
	30s smart balance board test
Upper body and shoulder flexibility	Back scratch test
Upper body strength and overall strength	Hand grip strength
Upper body strength and endurance	Arm curl test
Spasticity / increase of muscle tone	Modified Ashworth Scale (MAS)
Muscle strength	Medical Research Council (MRC) Manual Muscle Testing scale

Table 25 Usability & User experience questionnaires and instruments

Usability & User experience	
Variable measured	Tool
Usability	System Usability Scale (SUS)
	Enjoyment and usability scale
User experience	User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ)
Intervention acceptability	Acceptability of Intervention Measure (AIM)
Intervention appropriateness	Intervention Appropriateness Measure (IAM)
Intervention feasibility	Feasibility of Intervention Measure (FIM)
Feasibility and Acceptability	Feasibility and Acceptability Questionnaire
Technology acceptance	Technology acceptance measurement (TAM)
	Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology - brief version (UTAUT2-brief)
	Multi-Dimensional Measure of Trust (MDMT)
	The Robotic Social Attributes Scale (RoSAS) what measures
User satisfaction	Quebec User Evaluation of Satisfaction with Assistive Technology (QUEST 2.0)

5 Conclusion

This document presents information about the collection of data and analysis towards the creation of the Standard Version 1.0 for Living Labs in the Health and Wellbeing domain. This is the final stable version of the Standard produced during the VITALISE project. This version will be the starting point of the work of the ENoLL Harmonization WG that aims to release new versions every six months. The most important adjustment of this Standard Version is the List of updated terms in the Living Lab Lexicon, the integrated parts into Part 2, Living Lab Governance and Business Model". Within this section, we present the latest version of Living Lab Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), and added information about LL key activities, resources, cost structure, partner networks and channels. Additionally, revisions were made in Part 7, addressing Living Lab methods and tools. These modifications include the updated categorization of validated Living Lab questionnaires. The results of the VITALISE Harmonization process have already created impact to the community. Ten Living Labs (ThessAHALL, LAUREA, McGill-CRIR, INTRAS-MindLab, LifeSTech, LiCalab, IMEC Living Lab, CERTH-HIT, BAŞAKŞEHİR LIVING LAB) have already agreed to participate in the ENoLL LL Harmonization WG and 6 organizations and networks have declared their interest to follow the VITALISE Harmonization framework by signing a Letter of Interest.

References

Santonen T, Julin M, Hirvikoski T, Salmi A, Leskinen J, Saastamoinen K, et al. Living lab business models and services key findings from Product Validation in Health (ProVaHealth) project. Laurea-ammattikorkeakoulu. 2020.

ANNEX

Here we present the signed Letters of Intent for following the VITALISE Harmonization Framework.

Jagiellonian University

Dr Evdokimos Konstantinidis
VITALISE Project Coordinator
ENoLL – European Network of Living Labs
Avenue des Arts 6, 1210
Saint-Josse-ten-Noode, Brussels
Belgium

Subject: Letter of Intent to follow the harmonisation initiated by VITALISE project

Dear Coordinator,

We, Campus Living Lab, Jagiellonian University, had the opportunity to become acquainted with the VITALISE project (GA n° 101007990) and its activities, through our participation in ENoLL events and a study visit to THESS-AHALL.

We share the vision on the Living Labs need for a harmonisation framework allowing the achievement of more cost efficiency, optimal use of time and resources, and wider exploitation of research results from local communities.

We, Campus Living Lab, Jagiellonian University herewith confirm our interest and commitment to follow the harmonisation initiated by the VITALISE.

This Letter of Intent is not binding and shall become effective upon the signature.

Yours sincerely,
Wydziału Zarządzania i Komunikacji Społecznej
Uniwersytetu Jagiellońskiego

dr hab. Ewa Bogacz-Wojtanowska, prof. III

Name: Professor Ewa Bogacz-Wojtanowska, Ph. D

Title: Dean of the Faculty of Management and Social Communication at the Jagiellonian University

Date: 22 January 2024

Open Knowledge Foundation Greece

Dr Evdokimos Konstantinidis
VITALISE Project Coordinator
ENoLL – European Network of Living Labs
Avenue des Arts 6, 1210
Saint-Josse-ten-Noode, Brussels
Belgium

Subject: Letter of Intent to follow the harmonisation initiated by VITALISE project

Dear Coordinator,

We, Open Knowledge Foundation Greece (OKFNG), had the opportunity to become associated partners at the VITALISE project (GA n° 101007990) and its activities, through our support in the project events/ as part of the ENoLL network/ as we collaborated with VITALISE partners based on our expertise in open data.

We share the vision on the Living Labs need for a harmonisation framework allowing the achievement of more cost efficiency, optimal use of time and resources, and wider exploitation of research results from local communities.

We, Open Knowledge Foundation Greece (OKFN), herewith confirm our interest and commitment to follow the harmonisation initiated by the VITALISE.

This Letter of Intent is not binding and shall become effective upon the signature.

Yours sincerely,

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read "C Bratsas", is written over a horizontal line.

Name: Charalampos Bratsas

Title: Director and CEO Open Knowledge Foundation Greece

Date: 6/2/2024

European Network of Living Labs tVZW – mailing address: Avenue des Arts 6, 1210 Saint-Josse-ten-Noode Brussels
info@enoll.org - Legal Registry, N°: BE 0824 793 473

SOILL Framework partnership

Dr Evdokimos Konstantinidis
VITALISE Project Coordinator
ENoLL – European Network of Living Labs
Avenue des Arts 6, 1210
Saint-Josse-ten-Noode, Brussels
Belgium

Subject: Letter of Intent to follow the harmonisation initiated by VITALISE project

Dear Coordinator,

The SOILL Framework Partnership (GA 101112782) sets up and run an effective, agile, transdisciplinary, diffuse, open and fair one-stop-shop structure to coordinate, support, enlarge, and promote the network of 100 soil health living labs and lighthouses funded under the Soil Deal Mission and ensure their co-created user-centred, harmonized, reliable, impactful, replicable, and sustainable lead of the transition towards healthy soils.

Thanks to the mutual participation of both ENoLL and AUTH, the SOILL project and partnership had the opportunity to become acquainted with the VITALISE project (GA 101007990), its activities, and its results. The SOILL partnership shares the vision on the Living Labs need for a harmonisation framework allowing the achievement of more cost efficiency, optimal use of time and resources, and wider exploitation of research results from local communities.

I undersigned Giulia Campodonico, on my role of SOILL Project Coordinator, herewith confirm our interest and commitment to follow the harmonisation initiated by the VITALISE project in the definition of a framework monitoring and reporting structure to assess the maturity level of Soil Health Living Labs and their progress.

This Letter of Intent is not binding and shall become effective upon the signature.

Yours sincerely,

Giulia Campodonico
SOILL Project coordinator

oPEN Lab project

Dr Evdokimos Konstantinidis
VITALISE Project Coordinator
ENoLL – European Network of Living Labs
Avenue des Arts 6, 1210
Saint-Josse-ten-Noode, Brussels
Belgium

Subject: Letter of Intent to follow the harmonisation initiated by VITALISE project

Dear Coordinator,

We, VITO, had the opportunity to become acquainted with the VITALISE project (GA n° 101007990) and its activities, through the standardized evaluation framework developed by the project. This standard evaluation framework will be adopted within the oPEN Lab project to assess the maturity of the living labs involved in our project.

We share the vision on the Living Labs need for a harmonisation framework allowing the achievement of more cost efficiency, optimal use of time and resources, and wider exploitation of research results from local communities.

I, undersigned Maarten De Groote, on my role as Project Coordinator of the oPEN Lab project, herewith confirm our interest and commitment to follow the harmonisation initiated by the VITALISE project in the definition of the standardized evaluation framework to assess the maturity level of oPEN Lab living labs and their progress.

This Letter of Intent is not binding and shall become effective upon the signature.

Yours sincerely,

Name: Maarten De Groote

Title: Coordinator oPEN Lab project – Senior Expert Built Environment, VITO / EnergyVille

Date: 5 December 2023

GILL project

Dr Evdokimos Konstantinidis
VITALISE Project Coordinator
ENoLL – European Network of Living Labs
Avenue des Arts 6, 1210
Saint-Josse-ten-Noode, Brussels
Belgium

Subject: Letter of Intent to follow the harmonisation Initiated by VITALISE project

Dear Coordinator,

The GILL project (GA 101094812) develops a pan-European collaboration and learning hub – based on the Living Lab principles – as a one-stop-shop for tools, methods, and knowledge to reduce gender barriers in innovation and entrepreneurship, by enabling the transformation of individual, team, and educational practices. Nurturing the environment and skills needed to support Gender Responsive Smart Innovation and Entrepreneurship, GILL contributes to the creation of a fairer Open Innovation Ecosystem (OIE).

Thanks to the mutual participation of both ENoLL and AUTH, the GILL project and consortium had the opportunity to become acquainted with the VITALISE project (GA 101007990), its activities, and its results.

The GILL consortium shares the vision on the Living Labs need for a harmonisation framework allowing the achievement of more cost efficiency, optimal use of time and resources, and wider exploitation of research results from local communities.

I undersigned Dr Francesca Spagnoli, on my role of GILL Project Coordinator, herewith confirm our interest and commitment to follow the harmonisation initiated by the VITALISE project in the definition of Gendered Innovation Living Labs.

This Letter of Intent is not binding and shall become effective upon the signature.

Yours sincerely,

Dr. Francesca Spagnoli
GILL Project coordinator

Monash University

Dr Evdokimos Konstantinidis
VITALISE Project Coordinator
ENoLL – European Network of Living Labs
Avenue des Arts 6, 1210
Saint-Josse-ten-Noode, Brussels
Belgium

Subject: Letter of Intent to follow the harmonisation initiated by VITALISE project

Dear Coordinator,

We, Monash University (Australia), had the opportunity to become acquainted with the VITALISE project (GA n° 101007990) and its activities, through the OLLD conference and subsequent meetings with the VITALISE team.

We share the vision on the Living Labs need for a harmonisation framework allowing the achievement of more cost efficiency, optimal use of time and resources, and wider exploitation of research results from local communities.

We, Monash University, herewith confirm our interest and commitment to follow the harmonisation initiated by the VITALISE.

This Letter of Intent is not binding and shall become effective upon the signature.

Yours sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read "Sam Rye", is written over a horizontal line.

Name: Sam Rye

Title: Senior Research Officer & Lead of Monash Living Labs infrastructure

Date: 9 / 1 / 24